

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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EDITORIAL COMMITTEE

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (editor)
dippenaaransie@gmail.com

Ruan Booysen (PhD student, Univ. Free State)
booyesenruan@gmail.com

Dr. Leon Lotz (retired Arachnologist National Museum, Bloemfontein)
leonlotz57@gmail.com

Dr. Joy Paton (School of Life Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal)
joypurenature@gmail.com

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SANSA DATABASE—A WEALTH OF INFORMATION

The primary data accompanying each specimen in museum collections provide valuable biodiversity information to science and society. Most information about South African biodiversity originates from the country's natural history collections, which play a vital role in the Convention on Biological Biodiversity. However, natural history collections must be databased to manage this information and to make it available in an efficiently retrievable format that best meets the needs of science and society.

The first aim of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) was to collate all available information on South African spiders in one database. The following data sets were used:

- Primary data of all the voucher specimens housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the National Museum in Bloemfontein sampled during the SANSA and student surveys since 1972.
- Data extracted from scientific publications on all the species (2323) listed from South Africa, dating back to 1781 when the first species was described from South Africa. This includes information about all the species housed in 17 museums worldwide.

Extracting all possible information from the primary data documented with each specimen is essential. The primary data provides information on where and when the specimen was sampled and by whom, and it frequently includes also important behavioural and biological data. Unfortunately, most older species' descriptions are short, without illustrations, and often without exact locality data. With the large number of specimens more recently sampled during SANSA and other surveys and the availability of photographs a wealth of information is now available.

As part of SANSA, we have already revisited 76 spider species. We updated morphological information based on photographs of live specimens and, where possible, added behavioural data and more detailed locality data. We have also published more than 40 checklists of surveys undertaken in South Africa, and we were able to add for more than 200 species to the South African list on the WSC.

In this issue, we delve into this wealth of information:

- We discuss the significant role of the Frenchman Eugène Simon, who undertook the first spider survey in South Africa (1893), and list the 185 spider species he has described from South Africa.
- We revisited three spider species: *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781), *Ideocaira triquetra* Simon, 1903 and *Phrynarachne rugosa* (Latreille, 1804).
- Provide new checklist data for the Karoo National Park and the Pretoria National Botanical Garden.

CHAPTER IN BOOK

FOORD S.H., SCHOEMAN C.S., MUNYAI T.C. & ANDERSON A.N. 2024. Insect Conservation in Savannas. Chapter 20. 251–259 In: Routledge Handbook of Insect Conservation. Publisher: Routledge.
[doi:10.4324/9781003285793-23](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003285793-23)

ABSTRACT: Savannas cover almost a third of terrestrial Earth, but their exceptional biodiversity values are often underappreciated. Large tracts of temperate savanna have disappeared, while tropical savanna has been earmarked for agriculture. Contemporary threats include agriculture, altered disturbance regimes, resource extraction, inappropriate fire regimes, and global climate change. Less attention has been paid to the biodiversity consequences of woody plant encroachment, and this is a particular focus of our chapter. We explore the impacts of these processes on insect diversity and present case studies for three ecologically dominant taxa: ants, spiders, and beetles. We describe highly diverse and unique sets of assemblages associated with savannas that contrast with the relatively depauperate and generalist taxa in encroaching thickets. Savannas must be managed as ancient, highly biodiverse ecosystems, not as degraded forests that must be restored. Restoration of savannas would involve reintroducing disturbance regimes that create variability in tree densities. This would require local-scale management and regional conservation efforts, including large and strictly conserved core areas surrounded by buffers while retaining functional connectivity.

Photographs showing the Woody thickening over the last century near Louis Trichardt/ Makhado, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Photo credit: Norbert Hahn.

NEW PUBLICATION

HADDAD C.R. & VICKERS M.E. 2024. The genus *Baryphas* Simon, 1902 (Araneae: Salticidae) in South Africa, with the description of a new species. *Arachnology* 19(9): 1152–1164. [doi:10.13156/arac.2024.19.9.1152](https://doi.org/10.13156/arac.2024.19.9.1152)

ABSTRACT: The type species of *Baryphas* Simon, 1902, *B. ahenus* Simon, 1902, is illustrated and its distribution in South Africa is updated based on the material contained in six collections. A new species, *B. parvulus* sp. nov., is described from north-eastern South Africa. DNA barcodes (cytochrome oxidase subunit I, COI) are presented for seven *Baryphas* specimens and several other Plexippini from South Africa, with the results supporting the distinction between the two *Baryphas* species.

Baryphas baryphas Credits: P. Webb

Baryphas parvulus a new South African salticid species from Ndumo.

NEW PUBLICATION

HLONGWANE Z.T., MUNYAI T.C., MAJOLA O., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LAGENDIJK D.D.G. 2024. Diversity, composition and distribution patterns of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Sand Forest, South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology*, 62:e13334 13pp. doi.org/10.1111/aje.13334

ABSTRACT: Spiders are the dominant representative of the top predator guild in many terrestrial ecosystems, but their diversity and distribution in forests in South Africa are still understudied. This study aimed to determine ground-dwelling spider diversity, composition and distribution patterns in both sand forest and savanna (and their ecotone) using pitfall traps and to provide a spider species checklist for these three habitats in Phinda Private Game Reserve. A total of 410 individuals from 64 species and 21 families were recorded from the three habitat types. The Lycosidae family and *Pardosa crassipalpis* were the most dominant family and species. Spider abundances were similar between sand forest and the ecotone, but lower in savanna. However, species richness was similar across habitats. Spider species assemblages were similar between sand forest and the ecotone, but differed from the species assemblages in savanna. Spiders play an important role in food webs both below and above ground. Therefore, determining their diversity and distribution contributes to the overall understanding of the ecosystem in addition to promoting conservation efforts of key habitats such as the critically endangered sand forest.

Pardosa crassipalpis the most dominant species. 1. Male. 2. Female with egg sac. Credits: Peter Webb.

FOLLOWING ARTICLES PART OF GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN H. FOORD

SHERWOOD D., HENRARD A. & VAN DEN SPIEGEL D. 2024. *Selenogyrus foordi*, a new species and the first record of the subfamily Selenogyrinae Smith, 1990 from Guinea (Araneae, Theraphosidae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 37-48. doi.org/10.3897.AfrInvertebr.65.128284

ABSTRACT: A new spider species, *Selenogyrus foordi* sp. nov. (M,F), is described from Mount Nimba, Guinea. Consequently, we provide the first in vivo photographs of a selenogyrine in the scientific literature and the first record of Selenogyrinae Smith, 1990 from Guinea. We also record *S. aureus* Pocock, 1897, described from Sierra Leone, from Massif du Ziama Biosphere Reserve, Guinea, representing the second known species for this country.

Selenogyrus foordi

ARTICLES AS PART OF GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN H. FOORD

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MUNYAI T.C., SCHOEMAN C.S., HANN N. & FOORD S.H. 2024. Soutpansberg Mountain: a spider hotspot in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 85–114. <https://doi.org/10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.135136>

ABSTRACT: The Soutpansberg Mountain (SM) range in the northern part of the Limpopo Province within the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, is a refuge for high diversity of organisms due to its geological history and location. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), the spider diversity of the Soutpansberg Mountain was determined over 27 years: 58 families, 293 species, and 585 species were recorded. The Salticidae with 85 species, followed by Thomisidae (81 species), Araneidae, and Gnaphosidae, with 45 species each, are the most species-rich, while 11 families are represented by single species. Global distributions, endemism, and conservation assessment are provided for each species using IUCN criteria. Most species (516, 88.1%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern, whereas eight species (1.4%) are of special concern. Of these, five species are Rare and one each is Critically Rare, Vulnerable, and Near Threatened. Twenty-five new species have been described from the SM since 1997, but 17 species (2.9%) are still Data Deficient, and 44 species were not evaluated due to unresolved taxonomy. The SM represents a spider biodiversity hotspot in the Limpopo Province, representing 25.4% of the total spider fauna of South Africa and 64.3% of the known spider fauna of the Limpopo Province.

University of Venda students sampling spiders on the middle plateau of the Soutpansberg Mountain (SM).

Map of Soutpansberg Mountain (SM), showing the 16 sites (1–16) and Western Soutpansberg Transect (WST, red band) sampled under the supervision of Prof S. Foord, students and collaborators.

VAN DER MESCHT A.C., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. Completing the web: identifying sampling bias and knowledge gaps within South African spider surveys (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 223–246. <https://doi.org/10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.138881>

ABSTRACT: Species distribution datasets are fundamental for macroecological studies, although there is an overarching need to ensure that these datasets are representative of the entire community. Shortfalls, or knowledge gaps, within biodiversity datasets originate for a range of reasons, and can lead to incorrect conclusions or recommendations being drawn. Spatial scale influences the interpretations of diversity patterns and thus is an important aspect to consider. South Africa has a rich history of spider sampling and as such, it is possible to investigate the influence that scale, both spatial and taxonomic, has on the overall interpretations of how complete the spider knowledge base is in the country. To do this, we draw on curated natural history spider collections and determine how complete the spider assemblages are across twelve unique combinations of taxonomic and spatial scales. Overall, we received 121 605 usable records from seven collections, with spider records and diversity, being concentrated along the eastern and coastal regions of South Africa. We show that completeness scale with both increasing taxonomic and spatial scales, knowledge of the distribution of spider families at the biome level is largely complete. Moreover, we show that fine-scale knowledge of spiders assemblages in South Africa is relatively poor, yet we do identify, even at fine scales, assemblages in South Africa that can be considered complete. We identify under sampled regions of the country, which in turn are congruent with the distribution of under sampled regions found in other South African invertebrate groups.

Distribution of the individual spider database records across South Africa. Colours indicate the lowest level individuals are identified to (family, genus or species level).

ARTICLES AS PART OF GEDEKNSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN H. FOORD

AZARKINA G.N. 2024. *Foordus* gen. nov., a new genus of euophryine jumping spider from South Africa (Salticidae, Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 75–83. doi:10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.137760

ABSTRACT: A new monotypic genus *Foordus* gen. nov. with *Foordus stefani* sp. nov. as the type species is described. A short discussion on other Salticidae with disjunctive distributions is provided.

HADDAD C.R. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2024. On some new and poorly-known Chrysilini from arid western South Africa (Araneae, Salticidae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 127–159. doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.136083

ABSTRACT: Following a rapid biodiversity assessment of spiders in the arid western interior of South Africa, we report on the occurrence of some poorly known and new species of chrysiline jumping spiders. *Helafricanus patellaris* (Simon, 1901), *Heliocapensis capensis* (Wesołowska, 1986), *H. mirabilis* (Wesołowska, 1986) and *Menemerus lesserti* Lawrence, 1927 are recorded from the Northern Cape Province for the first time, and *Heliocapensis maluti* (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2014) (Lesotho) and *Heliophanus deformis* Wesołowska, 1986 (Angola) are recorded from South Africa for the first time, both also from the Northern Cape. The hitherto unknown females of *Heliocapensis mirabilis* (Wesołowska, 1986) and *Icius pulchellus* Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011 and the male of *M. lesserti* are described for the first time. Three new species are described: *Icius jacksoni* sp. nov. (M), *Menemerus foordi* sp. nov. (M) and *Natta triguttata* sp. nov. (M,F). One new combination, *Afraflacilla matabelensis* (Wesołowska, 2011), comb. nov. (ex *Pseudicius* Simon, 1885), is proposed. We present the first comprehensive molecular analysis of South Africa Chrysilini jumping spiders, based on the cytochrome oxidase I (COI) gene, which supports the monophyly of all but two genera (*Helafricanus* Wesołowska, 1986 and *Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833), which we briefly discuss.

The new species *Menemerus foordi*

MARUSIK Y.M. & HADDAD C.R. in press. A new species and new records of *Chumma* (Araneae: Macrobonidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates*

ABSTRACT: A new species of the genus *Chumma* Jocqué, 2001, *C. foordi* sp. nov., is described from the Western Cape, South Africa. New distribution records for *C. bicolor* Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018, *C. foliata* Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018 and *C. gastroperforata* Jocqué, 2001 are presented. The genus is recorded from the Northern Cape Province for the first time, extending its range extensively to the northwest by approximately 450 km. The distribution of all *Chumma* species is mapped.

The new species *Chumma foordi* male

ARTICLES AS PART OF GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN H. FOORD

JOCQUÉ R. & HENRARD A. 2024. A revision of Afrotropical *Asceua* (Araneae, Zodariidae), ant-eating spiders with puzzling distributions. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 161–198. [doi:10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.138029](https://doi.org/10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.138029)

ABSTRACT: The Afrotropical representatives of the zodariid spider genus *Asceua* Thorell, 1889 are revised. Apart from the known species *A. radiosa* Jocqué, 1986 (Comoros, Mayotte) and *A. lejeunei* Jocqué, 1991 (DR Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Nigeria), six new species are recognized and described: *A. arborivaga* sp. nov. (F Guinea), *A. foordi* sp. nov., (M,F, DR Congo, Guinea, South Africa), *A. incensa* sp. nov. (M,F, DR Congo), *A. luki* sp. nov. (M,F, DR Congo), *A. palustris* sp. nov. (F, DR Congo) and *A. ventrofigurata* sp. nov. (M,F, Tanzania). A key to the species is provided. Some of the species have a very large distribution, which is unusual in the Zodariidae. The phenomenon is probably linked to the canopy dwelling behaviour, which appears common in the genus but unique for this spider family.

New species *Asceua foordi*

Female

Male

NEETHLING J.A. & HARMS D. 2024. *Afrogarypus foordi* sp. nov. – a new pseudoscorpion species (Pseudoscorpiones, Geogarypidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 115–126. doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.137694

ABSTRACT: A new species of pseudoscorpion, *Afrogarypus foordi* sp. nov. (Pseudoscorpiones, Geogarypidae), is described in honour of South African arachnologist Stefan Hendrik Foord. The species is described from both sexes and known from near Fauresmith, Free State, South Africa. It is amongst the smallest species of *Afrogarypus* (chela length ca. 0.6–0.8 mm) and differs from its congeners by lacking trichobothrium isb on the fixed chelal finger, monotarsate legs I and II, and details of the galea and dentation of the chelal fingers.

New species *Afrogarypus foordi*

Female

Male

PÉREZ-GONZÁLEZ A. & MAMANI V. 2024. *Metalacurbs foordi* sp. nov., a new Lacurbsinae (Opiliones, Laniatores, Biantidae) from Ankasa National Park, Ghana. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 199–211. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.138398>

ABSTRACT: Despite being one of the most conspicuous African opiliones, the members of Lacurbsinae remain one of the least known groups of harvestmen species. All eight previously-known species of Lacurbsinae are inadequately described and poorly illustrated, leaving the morphological characteristics of this subfamily obscure. After more than half a century, we describe a new species of Lacurbsinae. *Metalacurbs foordi* sp. nov. is described, based on a male specimen collected in Ankasa National Park, Ghana, with a detailed description and illustration of its external and genital morphology. This marks the first modern taxonomic description of a species within Lacurbsinae, including an illustration and description of the male genital morphology, a crucial modern taxonomic characteristic for Opiliones and represents a starting point for the taxonomic revision of the subfamily.

Metalacurbs foordi

ARTICLES AS PART OF GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN H. FOORD

HADDAD C.R. (in press). And they just keep coming: four new genera of dark sac spiders from southern Africa (Araneae: Trachelidae). *African Invertebrates*.

ABSTRACT: As part of ongoing revisions of the Afrotropical Trachelidae, four new genera are described from southern Africa: *Foordana* **gen. nov.**, with *F. distincta* **sp. nov.** from South Africa (Eastern Cape, Free State, KwaZulu-Natal and Western Cape) as the type species, *F. flavipoda* **sp. nov.** from the Free State, *F. kasouga* **sp. nov.** from the Eastern Cape, and a fourth undescribed species from Zimbabwe; the monotypic *Mushimane* **gen. nov.**, with *M. tswibilinki* **sp. nov.** from KwaZulu-Natal as the type species; *Namaquella* **gen. nov.**, with *N. arida* **sp. nov.** from the Northern Cape as the type species and *N. samanthae* **sp. nov.** from the Western Cape; and *Rukuluk* **gen. nov.** from South Africa, with *R. gramineus* **sp. nov.** from the Northern Cape as the type species and a second undescribed species from KwaZulu-Natal known only from juveniles

BADENHORST H., HADDAD C.R. & JANION-SCHEEPERS C. (in press). Small-scale changes in spider and springtail assemblages between termite mounds and the surrounding grassland matrix. *African Invertebrates*.

ABSTRACT: The snouted harvester termite (*Trinervitermes trinervoides* (Sjöstedt, 1911)) is a widespread grass-eating termite species that constructs thermoregulated dome-shaped mounds. However, little is known about the influence of these mounds on the arthropod assemblage structure in the surrounding grassland matrix, and whether the mounds represent ecological islands. Spiders and springtails are two ecologically important arthropod groups often associated with termites or their mounds. We investigated their assemblage composition inside and around active and abandoned *T. trinervoides* mounds in a central South African grassland. In total, 838 spiders (59 spp., 22 families) and 217 857 springtails (24 spp., 9 families) were collected from 96 pitfall traps, placed at four microhabitats in and around each of 12 active and 12 abandoned mounds during March 2019. The most abundant and species-rich spider families include the Gnaphosidae (n = 270, 10 spp.), Zodariidae (n = 86, 7 spp.), Lycosidae (n = 86, 6 spp.) and Salticidae (n = 77, 5 spp.), whereas the springtail fauna was dominated by Brachystomellidae (n = 56521, 1 species), Bourletiellidae (n = 49573, 7 species), Sminthuridae (n = 44491, 3 species), Isotomidae (n = 32288, 1 species) and Entomobryidae (n = 26216, 7 species). Indicator analysis showed that the spiders *Zelotes sclateri* Tucker, 1923, *Heliocapensis termitophagus* (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2002) and *Scytodes elizabethae* Purcell, 1904 are associated with abandoned mounds, but no springtails showed an association based on the IndVal analysis of the eight microhabitats (lumped data), even though the undescribed *Cyphoderus* sp.

Sampling in the grassland.

were mostly collected inside active mounds. The mounds thus had a negligible influence on the spatial distribution of springtails in the surrounding grassland. The different spider and springtail assemblages sampled indicates that both active and abandoned mounds function as ecological islands in grasslands, but that mound size does not affect their abundance or species richness in the different microhabitats sampled.

An illustration showing the placement of the four pitfall traps in the studied microhabitats of a living mound: inside (purple), on top (green), at 0 m (red) and 3 m away (blue) from the *Trinervitermes trinervoides* mounds.

The role of savanna vegetation outside protected areas in the conservation of spiders

Despite the existence of nature reserves and national parks, there is a greater percentage of semi-natural and/or natural vegetation that occurs outside protected areas. Therefore, biodiversity studies that exclude these semi-natural vegetation types may underestimate arthropod diversity within the savanna biome. Furthermore, although there can be disturbances within the protected areas, the intensity is likely to be lower compared to anthropogenic disturbances occurring outside protected areas. Given the variation in the degree of disturbances, protected areas are often expected to support greater diversity of arthropods than the savanna outside protected areas. However, studies have shown that this expectation is not always the case because responses can vary based on taxon, vegetation type and region.

As such, two honours students (Sinenjabulo Gumede and Bonolo Maila) conducted mini-research projects in the savanna vegetation in Nduli Nature Reserve and at Walter Sisulu University, Mthatha campus, which represented the savanna outside protected areas. Sinenjabulo investigated if the savanna biome outside protected areas in Mthatha matters in the conservation of ground-dwelling arthropods. Bonolo compared ground-dwelling arthropods between the edge and the interior of Nduli Nature Reserve. Given that the savanna outside the reserve was exposed to greater anthropogenic disturbances than the edge (boundary) and the interior of the reserve, we determined if spider assemblages were affected.

Sampling using pitfall traps over a seven-day period took place in July 2024. There were 15 sites, five in each habitat type (outside the reserve, edge and interior of the reserve). The collection consisted of 131 specimens representing 45 morphospecies and 12 families of spiders. The Lycosidae was represented by 89 individuals and 19 morphospecies, while the Gnaphosidae was the second most abundant (14 individuals) and species rich family (six morphospecies). Other families were least abundant and species rich. These families were the Clubionidae, Entypesidae, Hahniidae, Mysmenidae, Orsolobidae, Oxyopidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae, Theridiidae and Zodariidae. We found no variation in species richness and abundance of spiders among the three habitat types. However, similarities in species composition of spiders were between the interior and the edge of the reserve only, while spider assemblages in both the interior and the edge of the reserve were different from assemblages in the savanna vegetation outside the reserve. Disturbance-sensitive and specialist species of spiders may have been negatively influenced by anthropogenic disturbances occurring in the savanna vegetation outside the reserve, thus variation in spider assemblages. However, we cannot ignore the fact that the savanna vegetation outside the reserve plays a role in spider conservation, as it supported species richness and abundance that were as high as that in the reserve.

Sinenjabulo Gumede and Chuma Guqa sampling in Nduli Nature Reserve.

We acknowledge that the high species richness and abundance of spiders in the savanna vegetation outside the reserve may have been due to an increase in generalist species. These results suggest that semi-natural and natural savanna vegetation outside protected areas can improve spider diversity.

CONTACTS: Sinenjabulo Gumede, Bonolo Maila, Tarombera Mwabvu and Inam Yekwayo (iyekwayo@wsu.ac.za)

One of the *Pellenes* species sampled from the Nduli Nature Reserve.

LINDA WIESE SANSA'S "CITIZEN SCIENTISTS" FROM THE EASTERN CAPE

Linda Wiese is the SANSA "Citizen Scientists" of the Eastern Cape. Over the past twenty years, she has contributed significantly to our knowledge of the Eastern Cape's spiders. She started collecting and photographing spiders, which began a long-term sharing of spider information and photographs of the Eastern Cape.

In 2005, Linda contacted me for assistance to identify spiders from Jeffrey's Bay. This eventually resulted in the first SANSA survey on the spider fauna sampled from an urban garden, and a checklist of 151 species from Jeffreys Bay was published (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

The garden in Jeffrey's Bay where the first surveys started and from where two new species were described.

Linda sampled widely in the Eastern Cape and checklists of Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022) and Jeffreys Bay (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023) were published followed by a checklist of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and the Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023).

She also made interesting behavioural observations and papers on *Walrencea globosa* (Pisauridae), *Phrynarachne melloleitai* (Araneidae), *Leucauge argyrescens* (Tetragnathidae), *Diaea albicincta* and *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* (Thomisidae) were so far published.

CONGRESSES

She participated in two AFRAS colloquia and presented a talk at the Thicket forum in Port Elizabeth.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2015. Spider diversity of the Addo Elephant National Park [poster & paper] Thicket Forum.

WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2014. Spider diversity of the Addo Elephant National Park (Paper). 11th Colloquium of the African Arachnology Society, Bloemfontein.

In 2010, she joined the SANSA team and was responsible for surveying Addo National Park (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014). This survey, which lasted several years, resulted in a checklist of 276 species of Addo (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2020).

Linda and Peter Webb at the AFRAS colloquium in the Free State.

The poster she presented at the colloquium and the Thicket Forum.

Linda in action in the Addo National Park sampling and photographing spiders.

In recognition of her contribution towards documenting Eastern Cape spiders two species have so far been named after her.

Mystaria lindaicapensis Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014.

Cheiramiona lindae Lotz, 2015

PUBLICATION CONTRIBUTIONS (L. Wiese)

WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2016. SANSA: Protected Areas - National Parks 3: Addo National Park. *SANSA Newsletter* 25: 6.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2020. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Addo Elephant National Park in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1), a1578. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v62i1.1578>

WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2021. Notes on the rare nursery-web spider *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 in South Africa (Araneae: Pisauridae). *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 19–20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5919476>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2022. More on the crab spider *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* Lessert, 1933 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 15–17. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146383>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., WIESE L. & WEBB P. 2022. First record of *Leucauge argyrescens* Benoit, 1978 from South Africa (Araneae: Tetragnathidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 11–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146657>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L. & STEENKAMP R. 2023. First record of the crab spider *Diaea albicincta* Pavesi, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 17–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828983>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., PAGEL K. & BUCK J. 2023. Notes on the crab spider *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 7–9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137402>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2022. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Thyspunt, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5916722>

WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L. & LOTZ L.N. 2023. Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 47: 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8420690>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., LOTZ L., & WIESE L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Garden Route National Park. *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 23–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878474>

INTERESTING SPECIES PHOTOGRAPHED BY LINDA WIESE

Philodromidae new genus and species from Thyspunt

First photograph of *Walrencea globosa* from Thyspunt

First photograph of *Diaea albicincta* from Addo NP

First photograph of *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* female from Addo NP

First photo of *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* male

VIDA VAN DER WALT OUR SALTICID SPIDER LADY

Vida van der Walt, with her macro photographs, played a significant role as a citizen scientist in SANSA. Although her main interest is the Salticidae over the last 20 years, she has also photographed numerous other spider families for SANSA. Vida went out of her way to collect, rear, and photograph Salticidae and to get them correctly identified with voucher specimens deposited in natural history collections. That enabled her to build up a broad database on the Salticidae. She used this information to develop a beautiful Salticidae website (<https://jumpingspiders.co.za/>), which earned South Africa international recognition. She has placed South African salticids on the map, especially with the photo of the little “sheep” spider (*Oviballus vidae*) named after her. Not only does she provide scientists with good photographs, but she has also lent a helping hand to several amateurs in identifying, photographing, and keeping salticids.

Vida's website <https://jumpingspiders.co.za/>

Vida traveled widely throughout Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and the Western Cape to collect salticids. She also participated in several SANSA surveys. She kept the immature spiders alive and spent hours feeding them until they became adults and could be identified.

Vida with the Pretoria SANSA team and some Spider Club members during a collecting trip at Enzemvelo Nature Reserve near Bronkhorstspuit.

Oviballus vidae Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 the salticid named after her. A second species *Diphya vanderwaltae* Omelko, Marusik & Lyle, 2020 of the Tetragnathidae also received her name in recognition of her contribution to science.

Her photographs play a very important role in SANSA and scientific papers. They are extensively used in:

- Posters
- Taxonomic revisions
- SANSA photo guides
- Books. The Spider Guide's cover and 236 photographs in the book, including all the salticids, were Vida's.

PUBLICATIONS (V. vd Walt)

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V. & WEBB P. 2022. New locality records for the white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 10–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915594>.

VAN DER WALT V., BLAKE B., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2022. Notes on the red beetle jumping spider *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 41: 7–9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6482732>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN DER WALT V.O. 2024. Gauteng urban area surveys 3. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Pretoria National Botanical Garden, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 52: 28–34.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V.O., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD S.H.1 & LOTZ L.N. IN PREP. The Salticidae of South Africa. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: Part 1 (A-Den) Version 1: 1–60*.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V.O., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD S.H.1 & LOTZ L.N. IN PREP. The Salticidae of South Africa. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: Part 2 (E-Ha) Version 1: 1–63*.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V.O., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD S.H.1 & LOTZ L.N. IN PREP. The Salticidae of South Africa. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: Part 3 (Hel-Iran) Version 1: 1–74*.

CONGRESSES:

VAN DER WALT V.O. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2017. Jumping spiders of the Diamond Route Reserves. 12th Colloquium of the African Arachnology Society, Western Cape Province.

ANOTHER SOURCE OF INFORMATION –ATLAS, BOOKS, GUIDES

Several books and guides have been published dealing with the arachnids of South Africa (1964-2024). The first one, by Dr Lawrence in 1964, was important as it opened a door to the spiders of South Africa. Although only a thin book called a Scientific Pamphlet it contains essential basic information. Unfortunately, many of the books listed here are not available anymore, but each of them contributed to our knowledge of arachnids.

BOOKS

1. **LAWRENCE R.F.** 1964. *A conspectus of South African spiders*. Scientific Pamphlet. Department of Agriculture. 64 pp.
2. **YATES J.H.** 1968. *Spiders of southern Africa*. Books of Africa. Cape Town. 200 pp.
3. **PRINS A. & LEROUX V.** 1986. *South African spiders and scorpions*. Anubis Press, Cape Town. 72 pp.
4. **DIPPENAAR A. & DIPPENAAR N.** 1987. *Spiders*. The insight series De Jager-HAUM, Pretoria. 47 pp. (Afrikaans & English).
5. **NEWLANDS G. & DE MEILLON E.** 1990. *Spiders*. Struik pocket guide to southern Africa. Cape Town. 64 pp.
6. **FILMER M.R.** 1991. *Southern African spiders: an identification guide*. Struik Publishers, Cape Town. 128 pp.
7. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & JOCQUÉ R.** 1997. *African spiders, an identification manual*. Biosystematics Division, ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook 9. Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 392 pp. [available on WSC]
8. **LEROY A. & LEROY J.** 2000. *Spiderwatch in Southern Africa*. Penguin Random House, Cape Town. 96 pp.
9. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2002. *Baboon and Trapdoor spiders of Southern Africa: an identification manual*. ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook 13. Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 130 pp. [available on WSC]
10. **LEEMING J.** 2003. *Scorpions of southern Africa*. Penguin Random House, Cape Town.
11. **JOCQUÉ R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2006. *Spider families of the World*. Royal Museum for Central Africa, Belgium. 334 pp. [available on WSC].
12. **GILDENHUYS P.** 2009. *A pictorial guide to the baboon Spiders of southern Africa*. Cadiz Street Publishing, Cape Town. 160 pp.
13. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN DEN BERG A.M.** 2010. *Spiders of the Kalahari*. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook No. 18. Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 120 pp.
14. **HOLM E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2010. *Goggo Guide*. Lapa Publisher (English). 304 pp.
15. **HOLM E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2010. *Goggo Gids*. Lapa Publisher (Afrikaans) 304 pp.
16. **FILMER M.R.** (revised by Larsen N.) 2010. *Filmer's spiders: an identification guide for southern Africa*. Penguin Random House, Cape Town. 128 pp.
17. **LEROY A. & LEROY J.** 2012. *Spiders of southern Africa*. Penguin Random House, Cape Town. 96 pp.
18. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R.** 2013. *Spiders of the Savanna Biome of South Africa*. University of Venda and ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. 134 pp.

19. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2014. *Field Guide to the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publishers, Pretoria. 424 pp.
20. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2014 *Spiders of the Grassland Biome*. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook No. 19. Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 120 pp.
21. **ENGELBRECHT I.** 2023. *Field guide to the scorpions of South Africa*. Penguin Random House.
22. **HAMILTON-ATTWELL V. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2023. *Spiders of the Fernkloof Nature Reserve*. Hermanus Botanical Society. 120 pp.
23. **DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S.** 2023. *Field Guide to the Spiders of South Africa*. Penguin Random House. 400 pp.

ATLAS

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Technical Report 2010 version 1, 1160 pp. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>

GUIDES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. 2020–2024. SANSa Photo guides to the spider families of South Africa. The following photo guides are available online and can be downloaded from Zenodo, World Spider Catalog or AFRAS Website. Families listed in red not available yet.

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. AGELENIDAE | 36. MICROSTIGMATIDAE |
| 2. ANAPIDAE | 37. MIGIDAE |
| 3. ANYPHAENIDAE | 38. MIMETIDAE |
| 4. ARANEIDAE [4] | 39. MITURGIDAE |
| 5. ARCHAEIDAE | 40. MYSMENIDAE |
| 6. ATYPIDAE | 41. NEMESIIDAE |
| 7. BARYCHLIDAE | 42. NESTICIDAE |
| 8. BEMMERIDAE | 43. OECOBIDAE |
| 9. CAPONIIDAE | 44. OONOPIDAE |
| 10. CHEIRACANTHIDAE | 45. ORSOLOBIDAE |
| 11. CITHAERONIIDAE | 46. OXYOPIDAE |
| 12. CLUBIONIDAE | 47. PALPIMANIDAE |
| 13. CORINNIDAE | 48. PENESTOMIDAE |
| 14. CTENIDAE | 49. PHILODROMIDAE |
| 15. CYATHOLIPIDAE | 50. PHOLCIDAE |
| 16. CYRTAUCHENIIDAE | 51. PHYXELIDIDAE |
| 17. DEINOPIIDAE | 52. PISAURIDAE |
| 18. DESIDAE | 53. PRODIDOMIDAE |
| 19. DICTYNIDAE | 54. PYCNOTHELIDAE |
| 20. DRYMUSIDAE | 55. SALTICIDAE [6] |
| 21. DYSDERIDAE | 56. SCYTODIDAE |
| 22. ENTYPESIDAE | 57. SEGESTRIIDAE |
| 23. ERESIDAE | 58. SELENOPIIDAE |
| 24. EUAGRIDAE | 59. SICARIIDAE |
| 25. FILISTATIDAE | 60. SPARASSIDAE |
| 26. GALLIENIILLIDAE | 61. STASIMOPIDAE |
| 27. GNAPHOSIDAE [3] | 62. SYMPHYTOGNATHIDAE |
| 28. HAHNIIDAE | 63. TELEMIDAE |
| 29. HERSILIIDAE | 64. TETRAGNATHIDAE |
| 30. IDIOPIDAE | 65. THERAPHOSIDAE |
| 31. ISCHNOTELIDAE | 66. THERIDIIDAE [2] |
| 32. LINYPHIIDAE | 67. THERIDIOSOMATIDAE |
| 33. LIOCRANIDAE | 68. THOMISIDAE [4] |
| 34. LYCOSIDAE [2] | 69. TROCHANTERIIDAE |
| 35. MACROBUNIDAE [see Amaurobiidae] | 70. TRACHELIDAE |
| | 71. ULORIBIIDAE |
| | 72. ZODARIIDAE |
| | 73. ZOROSPIDAE |

NEW SOUTH AFRICAN PUBLICATION

- AZARKINA G.N. 2024. *Foordus* gen. nov., a new genus of euophryine jumping spider from South Africa (Salticidae, Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 75–83. doi:10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.137760
- BADENHORST H., HADDAD C.R. & JANION-SCHEEPERS C. in press. Small-scale changes in spider and springtail assemblages between termite mounds and the surrounding grassland matrix. *African Invertebrates*.
- DAVIDS L., PRYKE J.S. & SEYMOUR C.L. 2024. The importance of heuweltjie patch isolation, size, and quality for arthropods in the Succulent Karoo, South Africa. *Ecosphere* 15:e70005. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.70005>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. Notes on the white running spider *Gephyrota glauca* (Jézéquel, 1966) from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 12–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766452>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & BOOYSEN R. 2024. Observations on the running spider *Suemus punctatus* Lawrence, 1938 from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 19–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1376653>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., EICHHOFF A. & CHRISTIAAN R. 2024. Observations on the black-faced huntsman spider *Olios correvoni nigrifrons* Lawrence, 1928 from Southern Africa (Araneae: Sparassidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 25–27. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766508>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LOTZ L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Golden Gate Highlands National Park, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766555>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2024. *The Zodariidae of South Africa*. Part 1 (A–D). Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 91 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.14404920
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MUNYAI T.C., SCHOEMAN C.S., HANN N. & FOORD S.H. 2024. Soutpansberg Mountain: a spider hotspot in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 85–114. <https://doi.org/10.3897/>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2024. Observations on *Chresiona invalida* (Simon, 1898) (Araneae: Macrobnidae) from South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 22–24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766436>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2024. Observations on the ground running spider *Hirriusa arenacea* (Lawrence, 1927) from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 15–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766491>
- FOORD S.H., SCHOEMAN C.S., MUNYAI T.C. & ANDERSON A.N. 2024. Insect Conservation in Savannas. Chapter 20. 251–259 In: *Routledge Handbook of Insect Conservation*. Publisher: Routledge Publisher: Routledge DOI: [10.4324/9781003285793-23](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003285793-23)
- GONZALEZ-FILHO H.M.O., COLPANI-SARTORI M.T., HENRARD A., GUADANUCCI J.P.L. & BRESOVIT A.D. 2024. Illustrated Catalog of African brush-footed trapdoor spiders: type specimens from the Royal Museum for Central Africa (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Barychelidae). *Zoosystema* 46 (26): 671–95.
- HADDAD C.R. in press. And they just keep coming: four new genera of dark sac spiders from southern Africa (Araneae: Trachelidae). *African Invertebrates*.
- HADDAD C.R. & VICKERS M.E. 2024. The genus *Baryphas* Simon, 1902 (Araneae: Salticidae) in South Africa, with the description of a new species. *Arachnology* 19: 1152–1164.
- HADDAD C.R. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2024. On some new and poorly known Chrysillini from arid western South Africa (Araneae, Salticidae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 127–159. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.136083>
- HLONGWANE Z.T., MUNYAI T.C., MAJOLA O., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LAGENDIJK D.D.G. 2024. Diversity, composition and distribution patterns of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Sand Forest, South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology*, 62:e13334 13pp. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.13334>
- HUBER B.A., SZYMAŃSKI H. & BENNETT-WEST A. 2024. Progress or burden? Formal description of every apparently new species available in collections is neither necessary nor useful. *ZooKeys* 1214: 77–90. doi:10.3897/zookeys.1214.130592
- JOCQUÉ R. & HENRARD A. 2024. A revision of Afrotropical *Asceua* (Araneae, Zodariidae), ant-eating spiders with puzzling distributions. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 161–198. doi:10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.138029
- MARUSIK Y.M. & HADDAD C.R. in press. A new species and new records of *Chumma* (Araneae: Macrobnidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates*.
- NEETHLING J.A. & HARMS D. 2024. *Afrogarypus foordi* sp. nov. – a new pseudoscorpion species (Pseudoscorpiones, Geogarypidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 115–126. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.137694>
- PÉREZ-GONZÁLEZ A. & MAMANI V. 2024. *Metalacurbs foordi* sp. nov., a new Lacurbsinae (Opiliones, Laniatores, Biantidae) from Anka National Park, Ghana. *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 199–211. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.65.138398>
- SAMWAYS M.J., PRYKE J.S., GAIGHER R. & DEACON C. 2024. Eco-evolutionary origins and diversification in a megadiverse hotspot: Arthropods in the Greater Cape Floristic Region. *Ecology and Evolution* 14: e70195.
- VAN DER MESCHT A.C., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. Completing the web: identifying sampling bias and knowledge gaps within South African spider surveys (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 223–246. <https://doi.org/10.3897/afrinvertebr.65.138881>

The role Eugène Simon (1880 –1910) played in spider research in South Africa

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com).

ABSTRACT: Eugène Simon, the well-known French arachnologist, was a prolific spider taxonomist and identified over 4600 species in his career. To obtain specimens for his research in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Simon, who was rich enough, financed his collecting expeditions. He traveled to South Africa on an expedition between February and March 1893. This was the first expedition to sample spiders in South Africa. He frequently also received specimens from other researchers and local people. This enabled him to eventually describe 28 new genera and 185 new species from 42 families in South Africa between 1880 and 1910.

Keywords: expeditions, new genera, new species

Eugène Simon, is regarded as the father of araneology and the first arachnologist to produce a complete taxonomic framework. During his lifetime, he described 4650 species; in 2013, 3790 species were still valid (Platnick & Raven, 2013; Mammola *et al.*, 2017). To obtain specimens for his research in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Simon, who was rich enough, financed his own collecting expeditions. This enabled him to travel worldwide when such expeditions were arduous.

Simon also regularly received spider specimens collected by visiting scientists and local South Africans. The more well-known collectors were Dr. Brauns, Dr. Casalis, Dr. G.A.K. Marshall, Dr. C. Martin, Dr. A. Penther, Dr. Hans Schinz, Dr. L. Schultze and Dr. I. Trägårdh. In the new species descriptions, Simon acknowledged them as collectors, and he frequently named species after them (Table 1). The first species he described from South Africa was the sparassid *Olios zulu* Simon, 1880 the type specimen from the Northern Cape was donated by Dr Casalis.

In 1893, he traveled to South Africa on an expedition to collect specimens (Lawrence, 1977). This expedition took place between February and March 1893. Little is known about his travels. He possibly traveled by railway and horse-drawn carriages. At that stage, South Africa was developing its new railway network, and the line between Cape Town and Johannesburg was only completed in 1892, and the link to Pretoria in 1893.

During this expedition, he collected a large number of spiders. From all the specimens available to him, Simon described 28 new genera and 185 species from 42 families (Table 1). Describing all these spider species was a valuable first step in documenting the spiders of South Africa.

However, as with most of the older species' descriptions, the descriptions consist usually only of a few lines without any drawings. To complicate matters further, while traveling in South Africa, many of the primary locality data for specimens collected were not well documented. Only 46 % of the species the towns noted, while the rest were only labeled as "Africa australis: promo Bonae Spei; Transvaal, Natal, Zululand or Cape" (Table 1). Most of the types are housed in the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle in Paris.

Eugène Simon

Photo credit: en.wikipedia.org

Simon's spider taxonomic framework for families and genera was embodied in *Histoire naturelle des araignées* (1892-1903). It took 11 years to publish the two volumes of 1000 pages each. At the same time, he continued with descriptive work. The 185 South African species were published in 22 scientific papers, mainly in French (see p. 12). Nine South African species were named "simoni" by other researchers to recognize his work. He died on 17 November 1924 at the age of 76.

In South Africa, practicing arachnologists try to recollect and redescribe all the older species. Of the 185 species described by Simon, 141 species (76%) have been re-examined, and more morphological information with illustrations is now available with more detailed locality data. Unfortunately, the type specimens for a few species are immature, complicating the process.

Simon's South African expedition in 1893 was the first effort undertaken to discover and describe our rich spider fauna. It is recognized as an important contribution to South African arachnology.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LOTZ L.N., BOOYSEN R., STEENKAMP R.C. & FOORD S.H. 2023. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 64(3): 221–289.

LAWRENCE R.F. 1977. Insects, Arachnids and Peripatus. Chapter 5 (109-131) in: A history of Scientific Endeavour in South Africa ed. Brown, A.C.

MAMMOLA S., MICHALIK P., HEBETS E.A. & ISAIA M. 2017. Record breaking achievements by spiders and the scientists who study them. *PeerJ* 5: e3972; DOI 10.7717/peerj.3972

PLATNICK N.I. & RAVEN, R.J. 2013. Spider Systematics: Past and Future. *Zootaxa*. 3683 (5): 595–600.

REFERENCES OF E. SIMON ON SOUTH AFRICAN SPECIES

SIMON E. 1880. Révision de la famille des Sparassidae Arachnides (Actes de la Société Linnéenne de Bordeaux 34: 223–351.

SIMON E. 1884. Description d'une nouvelle famille de l'ordre des Araneae (Bradystichidae). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 28: 297–301.

SIMON E. 1886. Etudes arachnologiques. 18e Mémoire. XXVI. Matériaux pour servir à la faune des Arachnides du Sénégal. (: Descriptions de plusieurs espèces africaines nouvelles). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (6) 5: 345–396.

SIMON E. 1887. Etudes arachnologiques. 20e Mémoire. XXVIII. Arachnides recueillis dans le sud de l'Afrique par M. le docteur Hans Schinz. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* (6) 7: 369–384.

SIMON E. 1889. Descriptions d'espèces africaines nouvelles de la famille des Aviculariidae. *Actes de la Société Linnéenne de Bordeaux* 42: 405–415.

SIMON E. 1892. Etudes arachnologiques. 24e Mémoire. XXXIX. Descriptions d'espèces et de genres nouveaux de la famille des Aviculariidae (suite). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* 61: 271–284.

SIMON E. 1893. *Histoire naturelle des araignées. Deuxième édition, tome premier*. Roret, Paris, pp. 257–488.

SIMON E. 1894. Note sur les arthropodes cavernicoles du Transvaal. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* 63: 63–67.

SIMON E. 1895. *Histoire naturelle des araignées. Deuxième édition, tome premier*. Roret, Paris, pp. 761–1084.

SIMON E. 1896. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Clubionidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 40(9): 400–422.

SIMON E. 1897. Description d'arachnides nouveaux. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 41: 8–17.

SIMON E. 1898. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux des familles des Agelenidae, Pisauridae, Lycosidae et Oxyopidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 42: 5–34.

SIMON E. 1899. Description d'une araignée myrmécophile du Cap de Bonne-Espérance (*Andromma raffrayi* n. sp.). *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de France* 4(10): 179–181.

SIMON E. 1900. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Attidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 44: 381–407.

SIMON E. 1901. *Histoire naturelle des araignées. Deuxième édition, tome second*. Roret, Paris, pp. 381–668.

SIMON E. 1902. Description d'arachnides nouveaux de la famille des Salticidae (Attidae) (suite). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 46: 24–56, 363–406.

SIMON E. 1902. Etudes arachnologiques. 32e Mémoire. LI. Descriptions d'espèces nouvelles de la famille des Salticidae (suite). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* 71(1-2): 389–421.

SIMON E. 1903. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 47: 21–39.

SIMON E. 1904. Descriptions de quelques arachnides nouveaux faisant partie de la collection du Musée d'histoire naturelle de Genève. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 12: 65–70.

SIMON E. 1906. Etude sur les araignées de la section des cribellates. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 50: 284–308.

SIMON E. 1907. Etude sur les araignées de la sous-section des Haplogynes. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 51: 246–264.

SIMON E. 1910. Arachnoidea: Araneae (II.). In: Schultze, L. (ed.) Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. Vierter Band. Systematik und Tiergeographie. *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 16: 175–218

SOME SA GENERA DESCRIBED BY E. SIMON

Table 1: List of the South African spider genera and species described by E. Simon (1880-1910).

Localities as reported by Simon: Prom. Caput Bonae Spei (Cape); Promontrim Bonae Spei" translates to "Cape of Good Hope" in Latin; Africa australis: Prom. Bonae Spei! (South Africa); Transvaal; Zululand (Natal) Cap de Bonne-Espérance! Petit Namaqualand (Namaqualand).

SPECIES	LOCALITY	SPECIES	LOCALITY
1. ANAPIDAE		9. DRYMUSIDAE	
<i>Metanapis bimaculata</i> (Simon, 1895)	Cape	<i>Izithunzi capense</i> (Simon, 1893)	Cape
2. ARANEIDAE		10. ENTYPESIDAE	
<i>Ideocaira</i> Simon, 1903		<i>Hermacha purcelli</i> (Simon, 1903)	Stellenbosch
<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	Natal (Martin)	11. ERESIDAE	
<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	Port Elizabeth (Martin)	<i>Seothyra perelegans</i> Simon, 1906	Bothaville (Brauns)
<i>Nemoscolus obscurus</i> Simon, 1897	Transvaal	<i>Seothyra semicoccinea</i> Simon, 1906	Willomore
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	Transvaal	12. GNAPHOSIDAE	
<i>Nemaspiza</i> Simon, 1903		<i>Ammoxenus</i> Simon, 1893	
<i>Nemospiza conspicillata</i> Simon, 1903	Transvaal	<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893	South Africa (Martin)
<i>Ursa</i> Simon, 1895		<i>Aphantaulax australis</i> Simon, 1893	Port Elizabeth
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	Transvaal	<i>Asemesthes</i> Simon, 1887	
3. BEMMERIDAE		<i>Asemesthes subnubilus</i> Simon, 1887	South Africa
<i>Homostola</i> Simon, 1892		<i>Micaria chrysis</i> (Simon, 1910)	Port Nolloth
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	Zululand	<i>Micaria tersissima</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas
<i>Spiroctenus pardalina</i> (Simon, 1903)	Cape	<i>Setaphis sexmaculata</i> Simon, 1893	Kimberley
<i>Spiroctenus pectiniger</i> (Simon, 1903)	Matjiesfontein	13. HAHNIIDAE	
4. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE		<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	Cape
<i>Cheiramiona clavigera</i> (Simon, 1897)	Natal	<i>Hahnia laticeps</i> Simon, 1898	Simonstown
<i>Cheiramiona filipes</i> (Simon, 1898)	Natal	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	South Africa
<i>Cheiramiona simplicatarsis</i> (Simon, 1910)	Kamaggas	<i>Hahnia zodarioides</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape
5. CLUBIONIDAE		14. HERSILIIDAE	
<i>Clubiona aspidiphora</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	South Africa
<i>Clubiona biaculeata</i> Simon, 1897	Port Elizabeth (Martin)	15. LINYPHIIDAE	
<i>Clubiona capensis</i> Simon, 1897	Port Elizabeth (Martin)	<i>Mecynidis</i> Simon, 1894	
<i>Clubiona helva</i> Simon, 1897	Natal	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	Transvaal
<i>Clubiona limpida</i> Simon, 1897	Natal	<i>Notioscopus australis</i> Simon, 1894	Cape
<i>Clubiona natalica</i> Simon, 1897	Natal	<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	Makapan
<i>Clubiona nollothensis</i> Simon, 1910	Port Nolloth	16. LIOCRANIDAE	
<i>Clubiona valens</i> Simon, 1897	Natal	<i>Andromma raffrayi</i> Simon, 1899	Cape
6. CORINNIDAE		17. LYCOSIDAE	
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> (Simon, 1896)	Pretoria	<i>Arctosa albida</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape
<i>Corinnomma semiglabrum</i> (Simon, 1896)	Makapan	<i>Artoriellula bicolor</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape
<i>Messapus martini</i> Simon, 1898	Natal	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	Makapan, Bloemfon.
<i>Pronophaea</i> Simon, 1897		<i>Geolycosa nollothensis</i> (Simon, 1910)	Port Nolloth
<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	Natal	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	Transvaal
7. CYATHOLIPIDAE		<i>Lycosa capensis</i> Simon, 1898	Cape
<i>Cyatholipus</i> Simon, 1894		<i>Passiena auberti</i> (Simon, 1898)	Makapan
<i>Cyatholipus hirsutissimus</i> Simon, 1894	Matjiesfontein	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	Makapan
<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	Cape	<i>Schizocosa subpersonata</i> (Simon, 1910)	Komaggas
<i>Pokennips dentipes</i> (Simon, 1894)	Jamaica (but maybe error)	<i>Wadicososa manubriata</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape
8. CYRTAUCHENIIDAE		<i>Zenonina mystacina</i> Simon, 1898	Bloemfontein
<i>Ancylotrypa spinosa</i> Simon, 1889	Port Elizabeth	18. MACROBUNIDAE	
<i>Ancylotrypa zebra</i> (Simon, 1892)	Zululand	<i>Chresiona</i> Simon, 1903	
		<i>Chresiona convexa</i> Simon, 1903	Cape

SPECIES	LOCALITY	SPECIES	LOCALITY
<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	Pretoria	30. PISAURIDAE	
<i>Chresiona nigrosignata</i> Simon, 1903	Cape	<i>Euprostenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	South Africa
<i>Macrobonus caffer</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape	<i>Rothus vittatus</i> Simon, 1898	Cape
<i>Pseudauximus</i> Simon, 1902		31. PRODIDOMIDAE	
<i>Pseudauximus reticulatus</i> Simon, 1902	Cape	<i>Eleleis</i> Simon, 1893	
19. MIGIDAE		<i>Eleleis crinita</i> Simon, 1893	Cape
<i>Moggridgea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1903	Matjiesfontein	<i>Theuma aprica</i> Simon, 1893	South Africa
<i>Moggridgea quercina</i> Simon, 1903	Cape	32. SALTICIDAE	
<i>Moggridgea terricola</i> Simon, 1903	Stellenbosch	<i>Aelurillus cristatopalpus</i> Simon, 1902	Kimberley e.a.
20. MIMETIDAE		<i>Afraflacilla histrionica</i> (Simon, 1902)	South Africa
<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	Cape	<i>Afromarengo coriacea</i> (Simon, 1900)	Natal (Martin)
21. MITURGIDAE		<i>Araegeus</i> Simon, 1901	
<i>Coryssiphus</i> Simon, 1903		<i>Araegeus mimicus</i> Simon, 1901	Makapan
<i>Coryssiphus cinerascens</i> Simon, 1903	South Africa	<i>Baryphas</i> Simon, 1902	
<i>Coryssiphus praeustus</i> Simon, 1903	South Africa	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	South Africa
22. OECOBIIDAE		<i>Carrhotus singularis</i> Simon, 1902	Bloemfontein
<i>Uroctea quinquenotata</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	Makapan
<i>Uroctea schinzi</i> Simon, 1887	Keetmanshoop (Schinzi)	<i>Dendryphantès schultzei</i> Simon, 1910	Port Nolloth
23. OONOPIIDAE		<i>Euophrys capicola</i> Simon, 1901	South Africa
<i>Dysderina capensis</i> Simon, 1907	Cape	<i>Habrocestum albimanum</i> Simon, 1901	South Africa
<i>Dysderina speculifera</i> Simon, 1907	Bloemfontein ea	<i>Habrocestum flavimanum</i> Simon, 1901	South Africa
<i>Opopaea mattica</i> Simon, 1893	Cape	<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	Kimberley
<i>Orchestina cincta</i> Simon, 1893	Cape	<i>Helafricanus patellaris</i> (Simon, 1901)	Cape
<i>Pseudoscaphiella</i> Simon, 1907		<i>Heliocapensis claviger</i> (Simon, 1901)	Stellenbosch
<i>Pseudoscaphiella parasita</i> Simon, 1907	Cape	<i>Heliocapensis deserticola</i> (Simon, 1901)	De Aar
<i>Telchius transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1907	Makapan	<i>Heliocapensis redimitus</i> (Simon, 1910)	Kamaggas
24. OXYOPIIDAE		<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	Zululand
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1897	Transvaal	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	Cape
25. PALPIMANIDAE		<i>Hyllus flavescens</i> Simon, 1902	Natal
<i>Diaphorocellus</i> Simon, 1893		<i>Icius desertorum</i> Simon, 1901	Matjiesfontein
<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	Cape	<i>Langona manicata</i> Simon, 1901	Makapan
<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	Port Elizabeth	<i>Mogrus albogularis</i> Simon, 1901	Kimberley
<i>Palpimanus globulifer</i> Simon, 1893	Port Elizabeth	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	South Africa
<i>Palpimanus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Pachyballus castaneus</i> Simon, 1900	Natal (Martin)
<i>Palpimanus paroculus</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Pachypoessa</i> Simon, 1902	
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	Makapan	<i>Pachypoessa lacertosa</i> Simon, 1902	Natal (Martin)
26. PENESTOMIDAE		<i>Peplometus chlorophthalmus</i> Simon, 1900	Natal (Martin)
<i>Penestomus</i> Simon, 1902		<i>Phintella australis</i> (Simon, 1902)	South Africa
<i>Penestomus planus</i> Simon, 1902	Willowmore	<i>Phlegra albostrata</i> Simon, 1901	De Aar
27. PHILODROMIDAE		<i>Phlegra bairstowi</i> Simon, 1886	Port Elizabeth (Bairstrow)
<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	Transvaal	<i>Plexippus rubrogularis</i> Simon, 1902	Makapan
<i>Philodromus vulpio</i> Simon, 1910	Namaqualand	<i>Pseudicius musculus</i> Simon, 1901	Natal
<i>Thanatus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Pseudicius zebra</i> Simon, 1902	Port Elizabeth (Martin)
28. PHOLCIDAE		<i>Rhene foai</i> Simon, 1902	South Africa
<i>Smeringopus hypocrita</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas	<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	Makapan
29. PHYXELIDIDAE		<i>Thyene coronata</i> Simon, 1902	Zululand (Martin)
<i>Phyxelida</i> Simon, 1894		<i>Thyenula</i> Simon, 1902	
<i>Phyxelida makapanensis</i> Simon, 1894	Makapan	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	Zululand
<i>Themacrys</i> Simon, 1906			
<i>Themacrys irrorata</i> Simon, 1906	Natal (Martin).		

SPECIES	LOCALITY	SPECIES	LOCALITY
<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	Port Elizabeth	<i>Caesetius schultzei</i> Simon, 1910	Kamaggas
<i>Thyenula natalica</i> (Simon, 1902)	Durban	<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	Shiluvane
<i>Trapezocephalus capicola</i> (Simon, 1901)	Cape	<i>Cicynethus peringueyi</i> (Simon, 1893)	Cape
<i>Trapezocephalus peckhami</i> (Simon, 1902)	Cape	<i>Diores</i> Simon, 1893	
<i>Trapezocephalus transvaalicus</i> (Simon, 1901)	Pretoria	<i>Diores bivattatus</i> Simon, 1893	Stellenbosch
<i>Vicirionessa mustela</i> (Simon, 1902)	Natal (Martin)	<i>Diores radulifer</i> Simon, 1910	Steinkopf
33. SELENOPIDAE		<i>Heradida</i> Simon, 1893	
<i>Anyphops atomarius</i> (Simon, 1887)	Port Elizabeth	<i>Heradida bicincta</i> Simon, 1910	Steinkopf
34. SICARIIDAE		<i>Heradida loricata</i> Simon, 1893	Bloemfontein
<i>Loxosceles speluncarum</i> Simon, 1893	Pretoria (cave)	<i>Mallinus</i> Simon, 1893	
35. SPARASSIDAE		<i>Mallinus nitidiventris</i> Simon, 1893	Matjiesfontein
<i>Olios kruegeri</i> (Simon, 1897)	Pretoria	<i>Palfuria</i> Simon, 1910	
<i>Olios zulu</i> Simon, 1880	N Cape (Casalis)	<i>Palfuria retusa</i> Simon, 1910	Steinkopf
<i>Pseudomicrommata vittigera</i> (Simon, 1897)	Transvaal	<i>Psammoduon arenicola</i> (Simon, 1910)	Simonstown
36. THERAPHOSIDAE		<i>Psammoduon canosum</i> (Simon, 1910)	Little Namakwaland
<i>Augacephalus junodi</i> (Simon, 1904)	Shiluvane	<i>Psammorygma rutilans</i> (Simon, 1887)	South Africa
<i>Harpactira lyrata</i> (Simon, 1892)	South Africa ?	<i>Thaumastochilus martini</i> Simon, 1897	Natal
37. THERAPHOSIDAE		42. ZOROPSIDAE	
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	Transvaal	<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	Cape
<i>Phoroncidia capensis</i> (Simon, 1895)	Cape	<i>Phanotea</i> Simon, 1896	
<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	Transvaal	<i>Phanotea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1896	Bredasdorp (cave)
<i>Steatoda marmorata</i> (Simon, 1910)	Steinkopf		
<i>Theridion auberti</i> Simon, 1904	Shiluvane		
38. THOMISIDAE			
<i>Avelis</i> Simon, 1895			
<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	South Africa		
<i>Borboropactus squalidus</i> Simon, 1884	South Africa		
<i>Heriaeus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1895	Makapan		
<i>Holopelus albibarbis</i> Simon, 1895	Stellenbosch		
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	South Africa		
<i>Nyctimus trimeni</i> (Simon 1895)	South Africa		
<i>Simorcus capensis</i> Simon, 1895	Cape		
<i>Talaus limbatus</i> Simon, 1895	Makapan		
<i>Thomisops bullatus</i> Simon, 1895	Transvaal		
<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895	Makapan		
<i>Xysticus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	Steinkopf		
39. TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afrocto coenosa</i> (Simon, 1897)	Natal		
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	Natal		
<i>Capobula infima</i> (Simon, 1896)	South Africa		
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	Hammanskraal		
<i>Trachelas scopulifer</i> Simon, 1896	South Africa		
40. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Philoponella operosa</i> (Simon, 1896)	Cape		
<i>Uloborus planipediis</i> Simon, 1896	Port Elizabeth		
41. ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Caesetius</i> Simon, 1893			
<i>Caesetius flavoplagiatus</i> Simon, 1910	Steinkop (Schultz)		
<i>Caesetius murinus</i> Simon, 1893	Cape		
<i>Caesetius politus</i> Simon, 1893	Makapan		

Pycnacantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781) the first spider described from South Africa revisited (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Allen Jones² & Peter Webb³ ‡

¹ Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA Free State team member; ³ SANSA Gauteng Team member

ABSTRACT: *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) is the first species collected and described from South Africa. The type locality was only given as “Cap bona spei.” Surveys have shown the species to have a wide distribution, and it is presently known from eight provinces. With its very characteristic spiky abdomen, this unique spider is also known as the hedgehog spider. It is a very common grass dweller and one of the orb-web spiders known for their adapted and reduced orb-webs. More information on their morphology, lifestyle, distribution, and conservation status are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, reduced orb-web, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pycnacantha* Blackwall, 1865, is represented by species from Cameroon, Madagascar, Mozambique, Namibia, and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2024). The first species, *P. tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781), was described from South Africa. It was followed by *P. meadii* Blackwall, 1865 from Mozambique, *P. fuscosa* Simon, 1903 from Madagascar, *P. dinteri* Meise, 1932 from Namibia and *P. echinotes* Meise, 1932 from Cameroon.

These unique spiders have characteristic spiky abdomens and are also known as hedgehog spiders. A second genus, *Daturina* Thorell, 1877, having a similar spiky abdomen (Fig. 6), was described from Caffraria, an old name for part of the Eastern Cape, in South Africa. Simon (1895), in his generic reviews, synonymized the genus *Daturina* Thorell, 1877, with *Pycnacantha*. He found *P. meadii*, and *Daturina hystrix* Thorell, 1877 to be a junior synonym of *P. tribulus*.

A recent checklist of South African spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023), showed that *P. tribulus* was the oldest spider species collected and described from South Africa by Fabricius (1781), 244 years ago. The type specimen was collected by Dr. L. Schultze, who frequently sampled spiders for arachnologists. Unfortunately, no exact locality data was provided, only “Cap bonae spei.” According to Zimsen (1964), the type material of *P. tribulus* is probably lost or destroyed.

Very little has been published on *P. tribulus* since Simon's remarks in 1895. Meise (1932), who discussed the genus and described two species, mentioned that members of *Pycnacantha* resemble the fruit of *Tribulus terrestris*, an annual plant in the caltrop family (Zygophyllaceae) known to bear strong spikes (Fig. 10). Lawrence (1964) provided a photo of *P. tribulus* in South Africa, and Van Vuuren (1981) from Cradock published some observations on *P. tribulus*. Filmer (2010) erroneously inferred that they build small orb-webs. However, it was only through the report by Dippenaar-Schoeman and Leroy (1996) that information on the behaviour of *P. tribulus* became available.

This paper provides more detailed information on the morphology, lifestyle, distribution, and conservation status of *P. tribulus*.

TAXONOMY

Pycnacantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781)

Aranea tribulus Fabricius, 1781: 547 (f).

Pycnacantha meadii Blackwall, 1865: 351 (f) synonym

Daturina hystrix Thorell, 1877: 302 (f) synonym

Pycnacantha tribulus Simon, 1895: 892, 894, f. 958; Meise, 1932: 75; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013: 99; 2022: 45.

Figures 1–4. *Pycnacantha tribulus*. 1. Female from Mooinooi, dorsal view. 2. Female from Mpetsane, lateral view. 3. Eye pattern anterior view. 4. Eye pattern dorsal view. Credit. 1, 3-4. Peter Webb. 2. Allen Jones.

Figures 5–10. *Pycnantha tribulus*. 5. Drawing of female *P. tribulus* after Simon (1895). 6. Drawing of *Daturina hystrix* Thorell, 1877 (syn. *P. tribulus*). 7. Abdomen showing abdominal protuberances covered with a layer of short setae. 8. Front legs, showing strong setae. 9. Epigyne. 10. Seed of the plant *Tribulus terrestris*. Credits: 7. Allen Jones. 8. Peter Webb.

Diagnostic characters: Female. Size 8–12 mm. Colour resembles dry grass, varying from creamy yellow to pale brown (Figs 1 & 2). The carapace is slightly longer than wide and narrower in the eye region (Fig. 1); the fovea has a slight indentation and is covered with a dense layer of short setae. Eyes eight in two rows (4:4); lateral eyes situated close together on distinct protuberance (Figs 3 & 4); the four intermediate ones are seated on a narrow, prominent protuberance directed obliquely upwards and forwards. Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 14). Legs are moderately robust; the first and second pair are much longer than the third and fourth, the first being the longest and the third the shortest. Metatarsi 1 and tarsi 1 slenderer with a slight curve (Fig. 8). Abdomen cream to yellowish-brown, sometimes darker; sub-globose, convex above, project over the base of the cephalothorax, and is armed on the upper part and sides with about fifty sharp-pointed protuberances; of which two are usually more prominent than the rest, and they are unequally forked (Figs 1 & 5); the number of protuberances and their shape varies between specimens; they are dull-yellow, with a narrow dark band over the dorsal length, integument covered by dense short setae (Fig. 7). Epigyne is a narrow transverse orifice, and has a reddish-brown hue, that of the branchial opercula being yellowish-brown (Fig. 9). Male unknown. *Pycnantha tribulus* resembles *P. dinteri*, a species from Namibia, and the two species differ only in the shape and position of their eyes.

SURVEYS

The hedgehog spiders were sampled during SANSА surveys with sweep nets mainly from grasses and low vegetation in the Grassland and Savanna Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). The spiders resemble grass seeds (Figs 21 & 22) and blend in with their spiky bodies and colouration. They are very well camouflaged and are not easily seen. That can explain why there are so few records of *P. tribulus* on iNaturalist and other virtual museums.

So far, 50 specimens have been sampled and deposited into the SANSА database. They have been found widely throughout eight provinces of South Africa. Although the original type locality was given as *Cap bonae spei*, the species is uncommon in some of the Cape provinces. The only record from the Western Cape is from Gondwana Private Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck, 2023). The species seems to be absent from the Northern Cape.

Pycnantha tribulus is mentioned in several survey publications. In the Gauteng Province, it is listed in the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024) and Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023). The third author (PW) stationed in Gauteng photographed and sampled the species in Irene and Rayton.

Figures 11–14. *Pycnantha tribulus* female from Mooinooi in the North West hanging from a trapezium web with extended front legs waiting for prey. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 15–18. *Pycnantha tribulus*. 15. Female with a moth. 16. Female with egg sac. 17–18. Juveniles emerging from the egg sac. Credits: Les Oates.

Figures 19–22. *Pycnacantha tribulus*. 19–20. Juvenile from Irene, Gauteng showing the small still undeveloped protuberances on the abdomen. 21–22. Species resembling grass seeds in the field at Mpetsane in the Free State. Credit: 19–20. Peter Webb. 21–22. Allen Jones.

From the Limpopo Province, the species were recorded from the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009), and the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008). In the Free State, the species is included in the checklists of Golden Gate Highlands National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024) and at Mpetsane Conservation Estate, where the third author (AJ) is stationed, the species was observed and photographed (Figs 21 & 22), several papers have been published (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

They were sampled from several localities in KwaZulu-Natal, but only the Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010) checklist has been published. The same applies to the North West Province, with only the Kgaswane Nature Reserve checklist published (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024). In the Eastern Cape Province, Van Vuuren (1981) mentioned behaviour as observed at from Cradock. It was included in the Mkambati Nature Reserve list (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011).

BIOLOGY

The female produced three pale yellow drum-shaped egg sacs at intervals of about two weeks. The egg sacs containing 30–35 eggs are suspended on twigs (Fig. 16). The second instar spiderlings are shiny, dark brown with reddish-orange spots but without protuberances (Figs 17 & 18). The spiderlings remained tightly grouped in the vicinity of the egg sac. The tiny spiders were given moths, and the prey was accepted in 80% of the instances (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 1996). Frequently, more than one spider fed on the same moth. The third author (PW) photographed some spiderlings showing the undeveloped protuberances (Figs 19 & 20). The male has been sampled, but it has not yet been described.

FEEDING BEHAVIOUR

Hedgehog spiders use a reduced orb-web to catch prey. Only silk threads forming a trapezium remain of the original orb-web. The spiders rest on the grass during the day, and in the evening, she spins a U-shaped trapezium between two adjacent grass stems. Here, she hangs upside down from her hind legs. The front legs are stretched out, and the prey is grasped in flight (Figs 11–15).

Web reduction results in the loss of prey-detection capabilities, and the spider must compensate for this somehow. Without the help of silk threads, the spider must develop a way to attract, detect, and capture winged prey by manipulating the reduced threads or using a substance to attract prey.

This group of spiders with reduced orb-webs is suspected to produce mimetic pheromones that attract male moths, which are grabbed with the forelegs (Fig. 15). Sometimes, prey is wrapped in silk before feeding commences. The strong macrosetae on the legs help to hold the prey (Fig. 8). Several genera (*Kaira*, *Poltya* and *Pycnacantha*) which are now known to prey mainly on moths have these strong setae on their legs (Stowe, 1986; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 1996).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Qachas Nek-Matatiele (-30.117, 28.683); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Fish River (-33.6, 26.85); Cradock (-32.16, 25.61). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-28.9, 26.12); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.8, 27.65); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.510, 28.617). **Gauteng:** Carletonville (-26.36, 27.4); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (-26.08, 27.85); Irene (veld opposite Gem Village) (-25.872, 28.225); Rayton (-25.74, 28.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Thanda Private Game Reserve (-27.87, 32.13); Midlands (-29.677, 29.922); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29) Mosdene Nature Reserve, Naboomspruit (-24.6, 28.78). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Kruger National Park (-25.01, 31.97); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Dullstroom (-24.42, 30.10). **North West:** Dikhololo Nature Reserve (-25.5, 27.78); Kgaswane Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Mooiooi (-25.756, 27.567). **Western Cape:** Gondwana Game Reserve, SE Herbertsdale (-34.07, 21.91).

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide range and there are no significant threats to the species it is therefore listed as Least Concern. The species is included in the following published check lists: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019), Gondwana Private Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck, 2023); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2024) and Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023).

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REFERENCES

- BLACKWALL J. 1865. Descriptions of recently discovered species and characters of a new genus, of Araneida from the east of Central Africa. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* 3) 16(95): 336–352.
- DIPPENAAR S.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MODIBA M.A. & KHOZA T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10–17.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831547>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & BUCK J. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Gondwana Private Game Reserve, in the Western Cape, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137378>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2013. *Spiders of the Savanna Biome*. University of Venda & Agricultural Research Council, 134 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2014. *Spiders of the Grassland Biome*. Plant Protection Handbook no. 19, Agricultural Research Council, 120 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L. N. & WEBB P. 2022. *The Araneidae of South Africa*. Version 2: part 3 (Ne-U). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 66 pp. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326991](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6326991)
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HAMER M. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. Spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the vegetation layer of the Mkam-bati Nature Reserve, Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Koedoe* 53(1), Art. #1058, 10 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v53i1.1058>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JONES A., HADDAD C.R. & LOTZ L. 2021. Grassland spiders of the Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 38: 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5947724>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LEROY A. 1996. Notes on the biology of *Pycnantha tribulus*, another araneid without an orbweb (Araneae: Araneidae). *Revue Suisse de Zoologie*, vol. hors série: 165–171.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A. & PRENDINI L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50(1): 1–9 .
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2023. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539738>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 50: 28–37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11526770>
- EITERSHANK G. 1964. Adhesiveness of spider silk. *Science* 146: 1058–1061.
- FILMER M. 2010. *Filmer's Spiders an identification guide to southern Africa* (Revised by Norman Larsen). Struik Nature. 128 pp.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., SCHOE-MAN C., HAHN N. & LYLE R. 2019. Spider checklist for the Blouberg, in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, South Africa. *Bothalia* 49(1), [a2455.https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455](https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455)
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the South African Grassland Biome. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*. 68 (2): 97–122.
- HADDAD C.R., HONIBALL A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & SLOTOW R. 2010. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in the endemic sand forest, Maputaland South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.
- LAWRENCE R.F. 1964. *A conspectus of South African spiders*. Scientific Pamphlet. Department of Agriculture. 64 pp.
- LEVI H.W. 1980. Orb webs: primitive or specialized. *Proceedings of the International Congress of Arachnology* 8: 367–370.
- MEISE W. 1932. Über die Stachelspinnen der Gattung *Pycnantha* Blackw. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 100: 73–79.
- ROBINSON M.H. & ROBINSON B. 1970. Prey caught by a sample population of the spider *Argiope argentata* (Araneae: Araneidae) in Panama: a years' census data. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 49: 345–357.
- SIMON E. 1895. *Histoire naturelle des araignées. Deuxième édition, tome premier*. Roret, Paris, pp. 761–1084. [doi:10.5962/bhl.title.51973](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.51973)
- STOWE M.K. 1986. Prey specialization in the Araneidae. In: Spiders webs, behaviour, and evolution (W.A. Shear ed.) *Stanford University Press, California*, 492 pp.
- THORELL T. 1877. Due ragni esotici descritti. *Annali del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Genova* 9: 301–310.
- VAN VUUREN, J. 1981. An interesting spider from Cradock. *Newsletter of the Spider Club of southern Africa* 22: 3-5.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2024. World Spider Catalog. Version 25.5. Natural History Museum Bern, at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on {date of access}. [doi: 10.24436/2](https://doi.org/10.24436/2)
- ZIMSEN E. 1964. Araneae. In: The type material of I. C. Fabricius. Munksgaard, Copenhagen, pp. 635–637.

Ideocaira transversa Simon, 1903 a unique spider species from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Peter Webb²‡

¹ Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA Gauteng team member

ABSTRACT: The species *Ideocaira transversa* Simon, 1903, was described from South Africa 122 years ago. The description based only on the female was short, and no drawings were provided. Nothing is known about this unique species. Based on specimens sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida and photographs of live specimens, we can add to the general morphology and discuss their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Ideocaira* Simon, 1903 currently contains two species: *Ideocaira transversa* Simon, 1903, known only from the female with type locality given only as Natal, South Africa and *I. triquetra* Simon, 1903, a species known from both sexes with Port Elizabeth as the type locality in the Eastern Cape. Since their descriptions 122 years ago, nothing has been reported on them. It was only after the publication of Smith (2005) that we were able to recognise the *Ideocaira* species.

Large areas in South Africa were surveyed during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), and numerous specimens were sampled. Some of the specimens sampled and photographed were identified as *I. transversa*. However, the species' original description was short and without drawings.

In this paper, we provide additional morphological data based on photographs of live specimens and show the colour variations based on specimens sampled and photographs taken by the second author (PW) from Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

Specimens were obtained during the SANSA surveys, and voucher specimens were deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). Additional information was obtained from the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Ideocaira transversa Simon, 1903

Ideocaira transversa Simon, 1903: 26 (Df); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 24 (f).

Diagnostic characters: Female: Length 7-8 mm. Cephalothorax: reddish-brown; carapace longer than wide; triangular shaped, anterior pointed (Figs 1,3,5); cephalic region separated by Y-shaped deep and complete oblique groove (Figs 7,9); integument with a layer of long white curly hair (Figs 7 & 8). Eye area: eyes in two rows strongly recurved; median eyes closely grouped on tubercle; in dorsal view, only posterior median eyes visible; anterior median eyes on the ventral part of tubercle; lateral eyes closely grouped some distance of median eyes. Chelicerae, mouthparts and sternum, reddish-brown. Abdomen triangular, truncated anteriorly, with lateral humps on each side; posterior tip rounded;

Figures 1–6. *Ideocaira transversa*. 1–2. Female from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal dorsal and lateral views. 3–4. Female from same locality dorsal and lateral view. 5–6. Immature male from Kloof dorsal and ventral view. Credits: Peter Webb.

colour varies from yellowish brown (Figs 1 & 2) to yellowish olive (Figs 3 & 4) to a very dark brown in an immature male specimen (Figs 5 & 6); integument with short hair denser on anterior edge; dorsum decorated with faint transverse bands; lateral humps sometimes with thin, short white stripes; posterior third of abdomen with thin white zig-zag bands with a double row of black spots on the interior edge. Legs same colour as carapace (Figs 2,4,6); four front legs are much more robust and longer than the others; patellae long; tibiae and metatarsi dorsally flattened and compressed; tibiae curved with relatively short spines dorsally and more prominent and unequal, arranged setae two rows (usually 6-7) ventrally (Fig. 10); metatarsi curved, with strong but smaller spines, especially numerous and almost disordered at the base. Epigyne (Fig. 11). Male unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Tsitsikamma National Park (Storms River Mouth) (-33.98, 23.83); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.2056, 24.7083); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0347, 32.425); uMkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6217, 32.2454); Kloof near Durban (-29.78, 30.86). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-34.07, 20.45).

RELATIONSHIP

Simon (1903), when he described *Ideocaira*, mentioned that the genus is closely related to *Kaira* Cambridge, 1889. Simon (1895) listed the following genera in the tribe Poltyini: *Cyphalonotus* Simon, 1895; *Homalopoltyx* Simon, 1895; *Kaira* and *Pycnanantha* Blackwall, 1865. Later he added the genera *Ideocaira* and *Micropoltyx* Kulczynski, 1911. His assemblage was based on the irregular form of the abdomen, slightly unusual eye arrangements and the strong macrosetae on the legs and that they prey on moths.

In a preliminary study, Smith (2005) examined the relationships of members of the tribe Poltyini as listed by Simon. She found several of the genera belong elsewhere, and *Ideocaira* occurs in a trichotomy with *Neoscona* Simon, 1864, and not with *Kaira*.

LIFESTYLE

Little is known about the lifestyle of *I. transversa*. Their morphological modifications, like colour and body shape, enhance their cryptic disguise, making them odd-looking spiders. When resting, the front legs are kept close together and folded together. The hind legs follow the contour of the abdomen. Nothing is known about their web-building behaviour, and from available photographs, specimens were frequently found hanging from silk threads swinging freely in the air, resembling a dried leaf (Figs 12-13). In one of the virtual museum entries, the photographer mentioned he had found the spider low down in dune forest in a trapeze-like orb-web.

Figures 7–13. *Ideocaira transversa*. 7. Carapace dorsal view. 8. Eye pattern anterior view. 9. Female dorsal view. 10. Front legs showing setae. 11. Epigyne. 12–13. Females showing them swinging in the air. Credits: 11. ASD. Rest Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide range and have been sampled from four provinces in South Africa. There is no known threat and they have been sampled from ten protected areas. Although the species is known only from one sex it is listed as of Least Concern.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): a review of current knowledge, constraints, and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L. N. & WEBB P. 2022. *The Araneidae of South Africa*. Version 2: part 2 (E-Ne). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 64 pp. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.6619195](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6619195)
- SIMON E. 1903. Descriptions d'arachnides nouveaux. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 47: 21–39. [doi:10.5962/bhl.part.25299](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.25299)
- SMITH H.M. 2005. A preliminary study of the relationships of taxa included in the tribe Poltyini (Araneae, Araneidae). *Journal of Arachnology* 33: 468–481.

First record of the theridiid spider *Theridion bicruciatum* Roewer, 1961 from South Africa (Arachnida: Theridiidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Peter Webb² ‡

¹ Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA Gauteng team member

ABSTRACT: The comb-foot spider *Theridion bicruciatum* Roewer, 1961, is known only from the type locality in Senegal. This species was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). Specimens were sampled from vegetation. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

Theridion Walckenaer, 1805, is the largest and most diverse Theridiidae genus, represented by 580 species (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Over the years, more than 380 *Theridion* species have been moved to other genera. In most countries *Theridion* must still be revised. Twelve species have been described from South Africa, but many more have been recorded and are still unnamed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), many theridiid specimens were sampled and photographed, but the major task was identifying the specimens. Based on Roewer's drawings and good description (1961), one species was eventually identified as *Theridion bicruciatum* Roewer, 1961. This brightly coloured species was described from the Niokolo-Koba National Park in Senegal and is known only from the type specimen. It was described as a *Theridion* species but might be moved to another genus after a revision.

In the Virtual Museums such as iNaturalist several specimens from South Africa are listed under *Chrysso*. However, no *Chrysso* species has been reported from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Levy, 1962). The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation.

TAXONOMY

Theridion bicruciatum Roewer, 1961

Theridion bicruciatum Roewer, 1961: 46, f. 10a–e (Df).

Diagnostic characters: Female: Size TL: 34 mm. Cephalothorax is shiny and smooth; the colour varies from brown in younger specimens with barely visible radial stripes (Fig. 1) to almost black in older specimens (Figs 3 & 4). Eyes in two rows of equal width; anterior row slightly recurved and posterior row procurved (Figs 8 & 12); median ocular area as long as it is wide, square-shaped (Fig. 8). Sternum uniformly reddish-brown to black. Abdomen highly arched, covering the cephalothorax from behind, rising dorsally to a blunt cone descending vertically (Figs 3 & 4); abdomen black dorsally and ventrally, with bright yellow-white broad bands over dorsal surface (Figs 1 & 4); a brown to black narrow median band cover whole length of dorsal surface, it is intersected by two narrow black transverse lines (Figs 1–4); posterior end with dark patch (Figs 11 & 14). Legs are uniformly pale yellow with widely spaced bands; leg 1 longer than IV (Fig. 1). Epigyne (Fig. 9) has a small scape in the middle, curving backwards. Juveniles: The juveniles' colour varies from almost white (Fig. 12) to decorated with paler yellow bands (Fig. 13) to solid bands (Fig. 14).

Figures 1–4. *Theridion bicruciatum*. 1. Immature female from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. 2–3. Female from Hluhluwe Game Reserve. 4. Female from Eswatini. Credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2–3. Ernst Klimsa. 4. Kate Braun.

Figures 5–9. *Theridion bicruciatum*. 5. Female abdomen lateral view. 6. Abdomen dorsal view. 7. Abdomen ventral view. 8. Eye pattern. 9. Epigyne. Credits: After Roewer (1961).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Senegal, Eswatini, Mozambique (iNaturalist) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Kwa-*

Zulu-Natal: Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87,32.16); Westville (-29.82, 30.92). *Limpopo:* Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). *Mpumalanga:* Barberton (-25.79, 31.04).

LIFESTYLE

Although the species have been recorded from three provinces it is rare in collections. Specimens were collected from leaves usually by hand. The second author (PW) sampled and photographed the species several times at Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve in the Limpopo Province (Foord *et al.*, 2016). The female makes a white egg sac with spikey edge that is deposited on the leaf surface.

CONSERVATION

The species is recorded from four African countries but is under sampled and are possibly present in more. In South Africa it is protected in three reserves.

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REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. 2021. The Theridiidae of South Africa. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide. Part 2 (R–T) version 1: 1-61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7515998>

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R. & WEBB P. 2016. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 58(1), 8 pages a1405. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v58i1.1405>

ROEWER C. F. 1961. Opiliones und Araneen, In Le Parc National de Niokolo-Koba, 2. *Mémoires de l'Institut Français d'Afrique Noire* 62: 33–81.

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2024. World Spider Catalog. Version 25.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 24 November 2024. doi: 10.24436/2

Figures 10–15. *Theridion bicruciatum*. 10. Female from Eswatini ventral view. 11. Female posterior end. 12–14. Juvenile specimens from Lekhalameetse Nature Reserve. 15. Female from Ndumo Game Reserve dorsal view. Credits: 10. Kate Braun. 11. Ernst Klimsa. 12–14. Peter Webb. 15. Ruan Booysen.

Observation on the bird-dung crab spider *Phrynarachne rugosa* (Walckenaer, 1805) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹

¹ Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The crab spider *Phrynarachne rugosa* (Walckenaer, 1805) was described as *Thomisus rugosus* from Réunion but has since been recorded from several African countries. Members of *Phrynarachne* have strongly modified carapaces and abdomens. Based on photographs of live specimens, the general morphology of the species and variation in colour and shape are discussed. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

Phrynarachne Thorell, 1869 is represented by 34 species and one subspecies and 10 of the species are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2024). The sit-and-wait crab spiders of the genus *Phrynarachne* have a striking resemblance to bird droppings. They spend much time sitting motionlessly on the leaves of plants, waiting for prey. However, by mimicking bird droppings in colour and shape, (Fig. 1) they are also known as bird-dung crab spiders.

Many Thomisidae have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Two *Phrynarachne* species have been recognized from South Africa *P. melloleitaoi* Lessert, 1933 (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022) and *P. rugosa* (Walckenaer, 1805).

Phrynarachne rugosa is an African endemic species described in 1805 as *Thomisus rugosus* from Réunion. The species has since been recorded from seven African countries (World Spider Catalog, 2024). The general morphology of the species is discussed based on images of live specimens, with notes on their colour variation, general behaviour, conservation, and distribution in South Africa.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Photographs were also requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum, and several photographs of *P. rugosa* from several localities throughout South Africa have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Phrynarachne rugosa (Walckenaer, 1805)

Thomisus rugosus Walckenaer, 1805: 33; Latreille, 1819: 42;
Phrynarachne rugosa Thorell, 1869: 37; Simon, 1895: 1045;
Pocock, 1898: 444; Ledoux, 2004: 176; Lehtinen, 2016: 154;
Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 44.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 5–6 mm, males 4–5 mm. Carapace as long as wide or longer; with Y-shaped oblique groove; clypeus broad and obtusely truncated (Figs 2 & 3); colour varies from greyish brown (Fig. 2) to reddish brown (Fig. 14) to yellowish brown (Figs 9 & 15); some specimens with broad mediolateral bands (Fig. 14); integument hard, unequal, grooved and bearing small humps; eye region narrower anteriorly; two equally recurved eye rows; lateral eyes raised on common elevations. Abdomen shape and colour variable; integument hard, unequal, grooved and bearing distinct round tubercles; frequently decorated with white patches; most specimens with pale narrow elongate medial patch in anterior third of abdomen (Figs 2, 12, 16); integument bearing short, stiff club-shaped setae (Fig. 3).

Figures 1–3. *Phrynarachne rugosa*. 1. Female on leaf from Knysna. 2–3. Females from Kloof near Durban. Credits: 1. Willie Meyer. 2–3. Bruce Blake.

Figures 4–8. *Phrynarachne rugosa*. 4. Eye pattern anterior view. 5. Ventral view leg 1. 6. Male palp. 7. Epigyne. 8. Male. Credits: 4. Bruce Blake. 5. John Richter. 6 & 7. After Ledoux (2004). 8. After Lehtinen (2016).

Legs thick and robust, angular and grooved; legs I and II stronger than rest; tibiae and metatarsi I and II almost the same length, flattened on the underside and armed with numerous robust, relatively short rows of spines (Fig. 5) ; tarsi with irregular and recumbent hairs (Fig. 10); tarsal claws sometimes robust, curved with 6-10 teeth; leg colour same as rest of body except patellae usually whitish (Figs 2 & 9); some specimens with white also present on femora (Fig. 3). Epigyne (Fig. 7). Males smaller than the female with anterior legs slender and armed with fine, very long spines (Fig. 8); palp with long thin retrotibial apophyses (Fig. 6).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: West Africa, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Malawi, South Africa, Madagascar, Mauritius, Réunion, Zambia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst Jeffrey’s Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Tsitsikamma National Park (-34.017, 23.878); East London (-32.965, 27.926). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Uvongo (-30.82, 30.39); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Westville (-29.824, 30.926); Port Shepstone (-30.688, 30.488). **Limpopo:** Soutpansberg (-23.016, 29.829); Blyde River near Hoedspruit (-24.405, 30.814). **Western Cape:**

De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Knysna, Diepwalle Reserve (-34.03, 23.03); Plettenberg Bay (-33.934, 23.605); Garden Route (-33.946, 22.464); Outeniqua Trail (-33.888, 22.967); Eden (-33.946, 22.464).

Figures 9–18. *Phrynarachne rugosa* females. 9. From Eden (Sally Adam). 10. Old silk patch. 11. From Kloof KZN (Bruce Blake). 12. From Knysna (Willie Meyer). 13. From Jeffreys Bay (Linda Wiese). 14. From Kloof (Bruce Blake). 15. Female (Len de Beer). 16. From Bathurst (John Richter). 17. From Hoedspruit (Wynand Uys). 18. From Bathurst (John Richter).

LIFESTYLE

Phrynarachne rugosa are plant dwellers and are predators that deceive prey by aggressively mimicking bird droppings (Yu *et al.*, 2015). They are seen during the day when they spend a lot of time sitting motionlessly on the leaves of plants, waiting for prey (Fig. 19). However, it could be dangerous to sit out in the open, but they have overcome the problem by mimicking the droppings of birds in color, shape, size, and smell, deceiving predators. The spider’s body has a glossy surface that gives it a “wet” look of fresh dropping, and the nodules on the body and rough edges of the legs further reinforce the look (Figs 12 & 14).

The masquerade is complete when they draw their legs close to their body and stop moving. They can lie motionless on a leaf for many hours (Fig. 1). Only when they become aware of prey are the front legs spread out for the attack (Figs 18 & 19). Research has also shown that *Phrynarachne* species may resemble bird droppings visually and chemically. Evidence shows these spiders sometimes smell like birds dropping (Yu *et al.*, 2015; Gray, 1991). The disguise also helps them avoid predators, as birds and other creatures are less likely to attack what appears to be their own droppings.

The spiders sometimes make an irregular patch of white silk on the leaves (Fig. 10), and when resting in the middle of this disk, they simulate a dried-up splash of bird droppings (Fig. 9) (Lawrence, 1964). However, from online photographs, it is clear that these silk patches are not always made.

Figure 19. *Phrynarachne rugosa* females from Uvongo
Credit: Jenny Cooke.

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide range, and no significant threats are known. It is protected in several protected areas; no conservation actions are recommended. It is listed in published checklists of the Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009), Jeffreys Bay (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023), and the Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2024).

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REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2020. *The Thomisidae of South Africa. Part 2 My-R*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 67 pp. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7513276](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513276)
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2022. More on the crab spider *Phrynarachne melleoitaoui* Lessert, 1933 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 15–17. [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7142162](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7142162)
- GRAY M. 1991. Spiders that smell. *Australian Natural History* 23: 190–191.
- HADDAD C.R., HONIBALL A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & SLOTOW R. 2010. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in the endemic sand forest, Maputaland South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., LOTZ L. & WIESE L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Garden Route National Park. *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 23–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878474>
- LAWRENCE, R.E 1964. A conspectus of South African spiders. Department of Agricultural Technical Services, South Africa. Science Bulletin 369, 64 pp.
- LATREILLE P.A. 1819. [Articles sur les araignées]. In: *Nouveau dictionnaire d'histoire naturelle, appliquée aux arts, à l'agriculture, à l'économie rurale et domestique, à la médecine, etc. Nouvelle Édition*. Deterville, Paris, Tome 30-36. [doi:10.5962/bhl.title.20211](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.20211)
- LEDOUX J.-C. 2004. Araignées de l'île de La Réunion: I. Hahniidae, Ctenidae, Thomisidae et Clubionidae (Araneae). *Revue Arachnologique* 14: 159–191.
- LEHTINEN P.T. 2016. Significance of oriental taxa in phylogeny of crab spiders (Thomisidae s.lat. and Stiphropodidae). *Indian Journal of Arachnology* 5: 143–171.
- POCOCK R.I. 1898. The Arachnida from the regions of Lakes Nyassa and Tanganyika contained in the collection of the British Museum. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 2(12): 429–448, pl. 13. [doi:10.1080/00222939808678518](https://doi.org/10.1080/00222939808678518)
- SIMON E. 1895. *Histoire naturelle des araignées. Deuxième édition, tome premier*. Roret, Paris, pp. 761–1084. [doi:10.5962/bhl.title.51973](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.51973)
- THORELL T. 1869. On European spiders. Review of the European genera of spiders, preceded by some observations on zoological nomenclature [first part]. *Nova Acta Regiae Societatis Scientiarum Upsaliensis* (3) 7(1, 5): 1–108.
- WALCKENAER C. A. 1805. *Tableau des aranéides ou caractères essentiels des tribus, genres, familles et races que renferme le genre Aranea de Linné, avec la désignation des espèces comprises dans chacune de ces divisions*. Dentu, Paris, 88 pp.
- WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2024. World Spider Catalog. Version 25.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 25 Nov. 2024. doi: 10.24436/2
- YU L., XU X., LIU F.X., JIAO X.G., CHEN J. ET AL., 2015. Field study of prey attraction by a bird dropping masquerading crab spider *Phrynarachne ceylonica* (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Acta Zootaxon Sin* 24: 35–40.

Gauteng urban area surveys

3. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Pretoria National Botanical Garden, South Africa

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Vida van der Walt² & Peter Webb²‡

¹ Project manager SANSA (dippenaaransie@gmail.com). ² SANSA team members Gauteng

ABSTRACT: The National Gardens constitute a large proportion of “green space,” they have principal conservation value for invertebrates. An annotated list of spider species known from the Pretoria National Botanical Garden is provided. A total of 152 species from 36 families and 113 genera are presently protected in the garden. The two most species-rich families are the Araneidae (23 spp.) and Salticidae (21 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (16 spp.) and Gnaphosidae (14 spp.), while singletons represent 15 families. Each species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status are provided. Most species (98.7%) have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern, while 1.3% are possibly new.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The formation of the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) in September 2004 through the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEMBA) proclamation provided the ideal opportunity to showcase the biological diversity held within South Africa's nine national botanical gardens. For years, the focus has been on studying and conserving South Africa's indigenous flora, and knowledge and understanding of faunal diversity are still lacking for many groups. The National Gardens constitute a large proportion of “green space” and have primary conservation value for invertebrates.

As part of the South African National Survey (SANSA), we have sampled several of the 11 national botanical gardens (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Our study marks a significant addition to the existing research on spiders in the South African National Botanical Gardens. The first paper on spiders in a South African National Botanical Garden was a survey by Tucker in the Kirstenbosch Botanical Garden, Cape Town, in 1920. Clark and Samways (1997) sampled a second botanical garden in Pietermaritzburg. Thirdly, the peri-urban Free State National Botanical Gardens in Bloemfontein was sampled by the staff and students at the University of the Free State and National Museum in Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). At the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, several surveys by the Universities of Stellenbosch and Cape Town (Pryke & Samways, 2009) were undertaken, and a final checklist was published by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2023).

This paper delves into the spider diversity of the highly significant Pretoria National Botanical Garden in Pretoria. We present a comprehensive checklist from the SANSA database on spiders sampled, including crucial information on the species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status.

STUDY AREA

The Pretoria National Botanical Garden (PNBG) (-25.737, 28.278) is situated in the eastern suburbs of Pretoria in Gauteng. It was established in June 1946 when the University of Pretoria granted approval to the Department of Agriculture to develop a botanical garden on land that was previously part of the University's Experimental Farm. This botanical garden opened in 1958.

The garden covers an area of 76 ha, and a 35 m high quartzite outcrop divides it into two sections: a frosty south-facing section and a north-facing, warmer section. A paved nature trail gives access to the natural vegetation on the ridge, which boasts a diversity of indigenous fauna and flora of different biomes and vegetation types.

Figures 1–3. Habitat types represented in the Pretoria National Botanical Garden (PNBG). Credits: Peter Webb

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collecting methods, identification, and voucher specimens: All three authors sampled spiders during short surveys. The SANSa surveys started in 2007, and the following sampling methods were used: pitfall traps, sweeping, tree traps (bubble wrap and corrugated wrapping), and active searching (Kassimatis, 2008). Occasionally Elizabeth Kassimatis (ARC) invited volunteers from the University of Pretoria and nearby schools to participate (Figs 4 & 5). The voucher specimens are in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA).

Endemicity value: The endemicity values for each species are provided in Appendix 1 based on their currently known distribution (Foord *et al.*, 2020). Seven endemicity categories are recognized:

- 6—species are only known from the type locality (PNBG).
- 5—species known only from the Gauteng Province (GE).
- 4—species are known from the Gauteng Province and an adjoining province.
- 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE).
- 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa (STHE).
- 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE).
- 0—also from outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons) or DD when there is a lack of distribution data. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC, while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 152 species, 113 genera, from 36 families, were recorded (Tables 1 & 3). As part of the Gauteng urban area survey project of SANSa, the first survey dealt with the diversity of the Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022), where 103 species from 31 families were recorded. In the second survey of the Waterkloof Nature Reserve, a total of 112 species, 84 genera, from 35 families were sampled. When comparing the two surveys, it was found that 42 species from 21 families were recorded from both reserves. Some of the species recorded are shown on pages 32 & 33.

Family diversity: Of the 37 spider families collected from PBNG (Tables 1-3), the two most species-rich families are the Araneidae (23 spp.) and Salticidae (21 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (16 spp.) and Gnaphosidae (14 spp.). Five families are represented by singletons.

Endemicity: Twenty-one species (14.1%) sampled at PBNG have a distribution wider than Africa, while 74 species (49.7%) are African endemics (AE), 23 species (15.4%) are Southern African endemics, and 29 species (19.5%) are South African endemics (Table 2).

Conservation status: A Lycosidae species and one of the Theridiidae are possibly new and were not evaluated. The rest of the 150 species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Pretoria National Botanical Garden with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.)

FAMILY	G	SPP.	FAMILY	G	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	16	23	Philodromidae	3	4
Bemmeridae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Phyxelididae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	3	Pisauridae	4	4
Corinnidae	3	3	Salticidae	15	21
Ctenidae	1	1	Scytodidae	2	2
Deinopidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	10	14	Tetragnathidae	2	3
Hahniidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Hersiliidae	1	1	Theridiidae	6	9
Linyphiidae	3	3	Thomisidae	8	16
Lycosidae	8	10	Trachelidae	2	2
Macrobuniidae	1	1	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Oecobiidae	1	1	Uloboridae	3	3
Oxyopidae	3	7	Zodariidae	3	3
				113	152

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Pretoria National Botanical Garden.

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	2	1.3
Data deficient DD	0	0
Least concern LC	150	98.7
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	21	13.8
1 – African endemics (AE)	76	50.0
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	24	15.4
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	29	19.1
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	0	0
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	0	0
6 – Type locality	0	0

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REFERENCES

- BUTLER V.P. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. Spider assemblages associated with leaf litter of three tree species in central South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Journal of Ecology* 49: 301–310.
- CLARK T.E. & SAMWAYS M.J. 1997. Sampling arthropod diversity for urban ecological landscaping in a species-rich southern hemisphere botanic garden. *Journal of Insect Conservation* 1: 221–234.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): a review of current knowledge, constraints, and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LE ROUX E., ROUX C. & LOTZ L. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, South Africa. *SANSa Newsletter* 48: 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258744>
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48:110–118.
- KASSIMATIS E. 2008. Surveys of the National Botanical Gardens: Pretoria National Botanical Garden. *SANSa Newsletter* 6: 5.
- NEETHLING J.A. & HADDAD C.R. 2013. Arboreal spider assemblages associated with four tree species in the Grassland Biome of central South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 123–131.
- PRYKE J.S. & SAMWAYS M.J. 2009. Recovery of invertebrate diversity in a rehabilitated city landscape mosaic in the heart of a biodiversity hotspot. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 93: 54–62.
- TUCKER R.W.E. 1920. Spiders of Kirstenbosch. *Journal of the Botanical Society of South Africa* 6: 21–24.

Figure 4–5. Elizabeth Kassimatis (ARC) with volunteers from the University of Pretoria and nearby schools, busy collecting spiders in the PBG in 2007.

Araneus apricus (Araneidae)

Prasonica seriata (Araneidae)

Neoscona subfusca (Araneidae)

Homostola vulpecula (Bemmeridae)

Copa flavoplumosa (Corinnidae)

Camillina cordifera (Gnaphosidae)

Allocosa tuberculipalpa (Lycosidae)

Oxyopes hoggi (Oxyopidae)

Peucetia striata (Oxyopidae)

Philodromus grosi (Philodromidae)

Vidole sothoana (Phyxelididae)

Rothus aethiopicus (Pisauridae)

Leucauge auronotum (Tetragnathidae)

Leucauge festiva (Tetragnathidae)

Orthobula radiata (Trachelidae)

Photo credits: Peter Webb

Cyrba nigrimana (Salticidae)

Holcolaetis vellerae (Salticidae)

Hyllus argyrotoxis (Salticidae)

Myrmarachne solitaria (Salticidae)

Pellenes bulawayoensis (Salticidae)

Rumburak laxus (Salticidae)

Thyene inflata (Salticidae)

Misumenops rubrodecoratus (Thomisidae)

Synema imitatrix (Thomisidae)

Thomisus citrinellus (Thomisidae)

Xysticus natalensis (Thomisidae)

Platyoides walteri (Trochanteriidae)

Uloborus plumipes (Uloboridae)

Cydreia schoemanae (Zodariidae)

Systemoplacis vandami (Zodariidae)

Photo credits: Salticidae and Thomisidae Vida vd Walt; remainder Peter Webb

TABLE 3: Spiders of Pretoria National Botanical Garden listing their endemicity (END), conservation status (CON), country endemicity (CEND)
LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered.

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE				DICTYNIIDAE			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Archaedictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
ARANEIDAE				ERESIDAE			
<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ammoxenus amthalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Asemesthes decoratus</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hyposinga holzapfelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus bicavus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes capsula</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	0	LC	C	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C	HAHNIIDAE			
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Paraplectana thorntoni</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	1	LC	AE	HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	LINYPHIIDAE			
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
BEMMERIDAE				<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE	LYCOSIDAE			
CHEIRACANTHIDAE				<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	<i>Arctosa</i> sp. new			NE
CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona pupillaris</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
CORINNIDAE				<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Hortipes schoemanae</i> Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000	2	LC	STHE	MACROBUNIDAE			
CTENIDAE				<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE	OECOBIIDAE			
DEINOPIIDAE				<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	OXYOPIDAE			
				<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
				<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
				<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
				<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
				<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1917	1	LC	AE
				<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
				<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
PALPIMANIDAE			
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE			
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
PISAUROIDAE			
<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprostenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprostenopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heliocapensis aberdarensis</i> (Wesolowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Heliocapensis charlesi</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Holcolaetis velleriae</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Myrmarachne solitaria</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DDT	SAE
THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Euryopis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion pictum</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. (New)		NE	
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE
THOMISIDAE			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE
TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE
ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Miagrammopes constrictus</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789)	1	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE

The spider diversity of the Karoo National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae): an updated checklist

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Leon Lotz²

¹ Independent Researcher, SANSA project manager, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ² National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa (retired)

ABSTRACT: In a Karoo National Park spider checklist published in 1999, 116 species from 37 families were listed. This updated checklist lists 148 species from 42 families, adding 32 species and five families. Information on the endemism and conservation status of all the species is provided. Most species (134) have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern; nine species are Data Deficient, and one is Rare. The family Araneidae was the most diverse, with 18 species sampled, followed by the Salticidae with 15 species and Thomisidae with 11. Thirteen of the families are known only by a single species. Karoo National Park is the type locality for two species.

Keywords: checklist, Nama Karoo, spiders, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

SANParks was formed in 1926 and manages 20 parks, covering over 3% of South Africa's total area. According to the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), SANParks' primary mandate is to oversee the conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, landscapes, and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks.

This study forms part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), which was initiated in 1997 to inventory the arachnid fauna of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). In 1997, the Agricultural Research Council registered a project (DIPSA 1296) at SANParks to determine the diversity of spiders in the different parks. Checklists for 10 of the 20 national parks have been published, and final reports are available for two more.

This paper provides a final Karoo National Park (KRNP) report. Since the publication of the previous checklist of spider species from the KNP (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), some additional species data from the park became available, and the material sampled by members of the National Museum, Bloemfontein is included. This checklist also provides an updated list of the latest taxonomic names for some species of the previous checklist and information on their endemism and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area: The KRNP is situated west to northwest of Beaufort West (32°11'S, 22°15'E) against the Nuweveld Mountain range in the Western Cape Province and comprises approximately 33 000 ha (Figs 1–3). The KRNP consists of four physiographic units: the southern and western plain 1200 m above sea level), the middle plateau (1200-1300 m), the mountain range (>1300-1900 m), and the northern upper plateau (1600-1900 m). It is a summer rainfall area, and the annual rainfall ranges from 175-406 mm with an average of 260 mm. It falls within the Nama-Karoo Biome. The vegetation includes Montane Karoo grassy shrublands, Karoo grassy dwarf shrubland, Karoo succulent dwarf shrubland, and riparian thicket (Figs 1–3).

Surveys: Collecting was undertaken by staff members of the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council, staff members of the National Museum in Bloemfontein, and SANSA team members.

1

2

3

Figures 1–3. Different habitats of the Karoo National Park (KRNP) Credits: Marie de Jager and T. Wiersmas.

Figure 4. Map showing location of the Karoo National Park (KRNP).

Identification: Both authors identified specimens. Due to new taxonomic information, several species that were previously only identified at the generic level are now identified at the species level. Additional information on species endemism and conservation status is also now available.

Voucher specimens: Specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida, ARC-Plant Health and Protection, Pretoria, and the National Museum, Bloemfontein.

Endemism value: The indices to assess the endemism value and conservation status of each species are: 6—species only known from the type locality (KNP); 5—species known only from the Western Cape, a Western Cape endemic (WCE); 4—species known from the Western Cape and an adjoining province; 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE); 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa (STHE); 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0—also from outside the Afrotropical Region (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

Conservation status: This value was determined for each species from a recent Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

LC: Least Concern when species have a wide distribution.
 DD: Data Deficient, through either a lack of distribution data or taxonomic resources.
 NE: Species Not Evaluated because they are immature or a possible new species or undetermined taxa.
 EN: Endangered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 148 species, 116 genera, and 42 families were recorded (Tables 1 & 4). Three species could not be identified at the species level as their taxonomy remained unresolved. The number of species is consistent with the faunal composition of most of the other national parks, which average 183.8 species per park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024).

Family diversity: Of the 42 spider families collected from KRNP (Tables 1 & 4). The family Araneidae was the most diverse, with 18 species sampled, followed by the Salticidae with 15 species and Thomisidae with 11. Thirteen of the families are known only by a single species. This pattern is consistent with the faunal composition of most of the other national parks. Some of the species sampled are shown on pages 38 & 39.

Conservation status: Of the 148 species sampled, 6.1% are Data Deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while four species were not evaluated (NE), indicating possible new species or species only sampled from juveniles. Most (134) species have a wide distribution and are listed as Least Concern (LC) (Table 2). Only one species, *Harpactirella karrooica* Purcell, 1902, is listed

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Karoo National Park (KRNP), with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled.

FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.	FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	3	6	Oxyopidae	2	4
Anapidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	2	2
Araneidae	11	18	Penestomidae	1	2
Bemmeridae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	4
Caponiidae	1	2	Pholcidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Phyxelididae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Pisauridae	2	2
Corinnidae	1	1	Prodidomidae	2	3
Ctenizidae	1	2	Salticidae	8	8
Cyrtachenidiidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Dictynidae	2	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Entypesidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	3
Eresidae	5	6	Sicariidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	10	15	Sparassidae	3	4
Hersiliidae	2	4	Stasimopidae	1	2
Idiopidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	2	2	Theraphosidae	3	4
Lycosidae	6	7	Theridiidae	6	9
Migidae	1	1	Thomisidae	10	11
Oecobiidae	2	2	Uloboridae	2	3
Oonopidae	2	2	Zodariidae	2	2
TOTAL: 42			116	148	

TABLE 2: Conservation status and of the spider species sampled at the Karoo National Park (KRNP).

CONSERVATION STATUS	SPP.	%
Not evaluated (NE)	5	3.4
Data deficient (DD)	9	6.1
Least concern (LC)	133	89.9
Rare	1	0.7

TABLE 3. Endemism of the spider species sampled at the Karoo National Park (KRNP).

ENDEMICITY	SPP.	%
0 – Africa and wider (C)	15	10.1
1 – Africa (AE)	41	27.7
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	43	29.1
3 – SA endemics (SAE)	28	18.9
4 – SA (SAE): 2 adjacent provinces	12	2.7
5 – Western Cape endemics (WCE)	5	3.4
6 – Known only from Karoo NP	0	0

Endemism: Of the species identified to species level only 17 (6.1 %) are South African endemics; 27.7% are African endemics and 29.1% are Southern African endemics while 15 species has a distribution wider than Africa (Table 3 & 4).

Five species are Western Cape endemics: *Orchestina cincta* Simon, 1893; *Penestomus kruger* Miller, Griswold, Haddad 2010 (Penestomidae); *Harpactira chrysogaster* Pocock, 1897 (Fig. 8) and *Harpactirella karrooica* Purcell, 1902 (Theraphosidae) and *Cicyne-thus peringueyi* (Simon, 1893) (Zodariidae). KRNP is the type locality of two species: *Penestomus kruger* and *Palystes karooensis* (Sparassidae) (Figs 6 & 7).

CONCLUSION

A total of 148 species have been recorded from the KRNP to date, and all of them included in the recently completed Spider Red Listing project and National Spider Checklist. The spider fauna of the park represent 6.4% of the currently recorded South African species. The nine species listed as Data Deficient require further collecting and monitoring to improve our knowledge of their distribution.

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REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LEROY A., DE JAGER M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spider diversity of the Karoo National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 42: 31–42.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): a review of current knowledge, constraints, and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LOTZ L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Golden Gate Highlands National Park, South Africa. *SANSa Newsletter* 51: 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766555>
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48: 110–118.

Figure 5. KRNP type locality of *Penestomus kruger*

Figures 6 & 7. KRNP type locality of *Palystes karooensis* Credits E. vd Westhuizen

Figure 8. A Western Cape endemic spider *Harpactira chrysogaster*. Credit: E. vd

Copuetta lacustris (Corinnidae) P. Webb

Paradonea variegata (Eresidae) S. Nesar

Seothyra scheineri (Eresidae) P. Webb

Ammoxenus pentheri (Gnaphosidae) M de Jager

Ibala arcus (Gnaphosidae) P. Webb

Zelotes lavus (Gnaphosidae) P. Webb

Tyrotama aridus (Hersiliidae) E. vd Westhuizen

Evippomma squamulatum (Lycosidae) P. Webb

Moggridgea peringueyi (Migidae) C. Haddad

Diaphorocellus biplagiatus (Palpimanidae) P. Webb

Hirriusa arenacea (Philodromidae) P. Webb

Euophrys leipoldti (Salticidae) P. Webb

Latrodectus karrooensis (Theridiidae) L. Oates

Heriaeus zanii (Thomisidae) P. Webb

Diores poweri (Zodariidae) P. Webb

TABLE 4: Spiders of Golden Gate National Park listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND). LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered.

SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE				ERESIDAE			
<i>Agelena australis</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE	<i>Dresserus schreineri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	DD	SAE
<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE	<i>Gandanameno purcelli</i> (Tucker, 1920)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Benoitia deserticola</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Paradonea variegata</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Benoitia raymondeae</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Seothyra schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Stegodyphus tentoriicola</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
ANAPIDAE				GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Crozetus rhodesiensis</i> Brignoli, 1981	2	LC	STHE	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
ARANEIDAE				<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes reflexus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Marinarozelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986	1	LC	AE	<i>Scotophaeus relegatus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes aridus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona quincasea</i> Roberts, 1983	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	0	LC	C	<i>Zelotes lightfooti</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Singa</i> sp. immature		NE		<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Tyrotama abyssus</i> Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005	2	LC	STHE
BEMMERIDAE				<i>Tyrotama arida</i> (Smithers, 1945)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Spiroctenus schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	4	DD	SAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
CAPONIIDAE				IDIOPIDAE			
<i>Caponia karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	4	DD	SAE	<i>Gorgyrella schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	3	LC	SAE
<i>Caponia spiralis</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	LINYPHIIDAE			
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				<i>Metaleptyphantes familiaris</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	LYCOSIDAE			
CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
CORINNIDAE				<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE	<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE				<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Ancylotrypa sororum</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
DICTYNIDAE				<i>Zenonina mystacina</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C	MIGIDAE			
<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE		<i>Moggridgea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE
ENTYPESIDAE				OECOBIIDAE			
<i>Hermacha evanescens</i> Purcell, 1903	3	DD	SAE	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
				<i>Paroecobius</i> sp. (juvenile)		NE	

SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
OONOPIIDAE			
<i>Oonops caecus</i> Benoit, 1975	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Orchestina cincta</i> Simon, 1893	5 DD	SAE	
OXYOPIIDAE			
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1 LC	AE	
<i>Peucetia crucifera</i> Lawrence, 1927	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1 LC	AE	
<i>Peucetia viridis</i> (Blackwall, 1858)	1 LC	AE	
PALPIMANIDAE			
<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3 LC	SAE	
PENESTOMIDAE			
<i>Penestomus armata</i> (Lehtinen, 1967)	4 DD	SAE	
<i>Penestomus kruger</i> Miller, Griswold, Haddad, 2010	5 DD	SAE	
PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0 LC	C	
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1 LC	AE	
PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Smeringopus ubicki</i> Huber, 2012	4 LC	SAE	
PHYXELIIDAE			
<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3 LC	SAE	
PISAUROIDAE			
<i>Euprostenopsis pulchella</i> Pocock 1902	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1 LC	AE	
PRODIDOMIDAE			
<i>Prodidomus purpurascens</i> Purcell, 1904	4 LC	SAE	
<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Theuma purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	3 LC	SAE	
SALTICIDAE			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1 LC	AE	
<i>Euophrys leipoldti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4 LC	SAE	
<i>Heliophanus pratti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1 LC	AE	
<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0 LC	C	
<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesołowska, 2006	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1 LC	AE	
SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes</i> sp. 1		NE	
<i>Scytodes</i> sp. 2		NE	
SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna hottentotta</i> Purcell, 1908	3 LC	SAE	
SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops hessei</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Anyphops immaculatus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Anyphops maculosus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3 LC	SAE	

SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
SICARIIDAE			
<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4 LC	SAE	
SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1 LC	AE	
<i>Olios machadoi</i> Lawrence, 1952	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Palystes karooensis</i> Croeser, 1996	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Parapalystes lycosinus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4 LC	SAE	
STASIMOPIIDAE			
<i>Stasimopus bimaculatus</i> Purcell, 1903	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Stasimopus maraisi</i> Hewitt, 1914	4 DD	SAE	
TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> Blackwall, 1866	1 LC	AE	
THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Brachionopus robustus</i> Pocock, 1897	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Harpactira chrysogaster</i> Pocock, 1897	5 LC	SAE	
<i>Harpactira namaquensis</i> Purcell, 1902	4 LC	SAE	
<i>Harpactirella karrooica</i> Purcell, 1902	5 Rare	SAE	
THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0 LC	C	
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0 LC	C	
<i>Latrodectus indistinctus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Latrodectus karrooensis</i> Smithers, 1944	4 LC	SAE	
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1 LC	AE	
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0 LC	C	
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1 LC	AE	
THOMISIDAE			
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1 LC	AE	
<i>Heriaeus zanii</i> Simon, 1895	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Holopelus albibarbis</i> Simon, 1895	1 LC	AE	
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1 LC	AE	
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1 LC	AE	
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1 LC	AE	
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0 LC	C	
<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Synema imitator</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1 LC	AE	
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1 LC	AE	
<i>Xysticus havilandi</i> Lawrence, 1942	3 LC	SAE	
ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Uloborus planipediis</i> Simon, 1896	3 LC	SAE	
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0 LC	C	
ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Cicynethus peringueyi</i> (Simon, 1893)	5 DD	SAE	
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2 LC	STHE	
<i>Mallinus nitidiventris</i> Simon, 1893	3 LC	SAE	

Expedition to sample arachnids in Angola

Tharina L. Bird^{1,2} & Ruan Booyesen³

¹General Entomology, Ditsong National Museum of Natural History, Pretoria, South Africa. tharina@ditsong.org.za; ²Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria, South Africa; ³Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa.

Earlier this year we had the privilege of going on an 18 day expedition to Angola (24 October – 11 November 2024). The expedition was part of the ongoing biodiversity survey of the Lisima Highlands in eastern Angola conducted by the National Geographic Okavango Wilderness Project and Wild Bird Trust. Other international scientists included three entomologists, a botanist and an ecohydrologist. Research was coordinated by Rob Taylor, an avid naturalist with a great interest in dragonflies, and Telmo Antonio, a botanist and PhD student. The expedition was led by Alfonso Lussati – referred to as *o chefe* (“the chief” in Portuguese), Alfonso’s word was law, as he was in charge of our safety – a huge responsibility given the remoteness of the areas we were working in, and given the threat of uncleared landmines. Logistics was well coordinated and smooth-running, with a dedicated cook and four drivers. This, plus a photographer, teacher, representative of the government, and student from Angola, brought the number of team members to nineteen. Lisima highlands remain largely undersampled due to 41 years of war (the Angolan War of Independence followed by the Angolan Civil War) that ended in 2002, and the remaining security risk of landmines. The aim of the expedition was to survey headwaters of three important drainage systems in Angola: the Kwanza, Zambesi, and Okavango rivers.

To cover the three drainage systems, we made camp east of Cuemba village (Kwanza system), on the banks of the Lungevungo River (tributary of the Zambezi), and on the shore of Cuanavale Lake (Okavango system). Getting to the collecting sites involved flying to Kuito on a commercial flight, driving vast distances to and between our basecamps, and flying back to Luanda from Tempué on a small chartered plane. Driving was through huge expanses of largely Miombo forest, with patches of savannah woodland, grassland and wetland ecotones. Collecting stops along the road ensured that we sampled a diversity of habitats.

The timing of the expedition was planned so that the bulk of the nights were dark moon. Although this was done to optimize collecting of nocturnal Lepidoptera, it was also advantageous for the collecting of scorpions. We collected five scorpion species, using UV detection at night, and digging burrows in the day. Species were identified by Lorenzo Prendini of the American Museum of Natural History, New York. *Parabuthus raudus* (Simon, 1888) and *Opisththalmus wahlbergii* (Thorell, 1876) were common in the sandy savanna and grassland patches. Both being Kalahari species, this is not surprising given that the Lisima highlands fall within the Kalahari Basin. Also in sandy areas were *Uroplectes carinatus* (Pocock, 1890). *Lychas asper* (Pocock, 1891) and *Uroplectes occidentalis* Simon, 1876 are forest species. We found these species only in good quality forests that had a healthy mosaic of leaf litter and mosses as groundcover. Both forest species are beautiful central African species that reach the southern limit of Angola and Zambia.

We also collected some false scorpions (Pseudoscorpiones), harvestmen (Opiliones), and solifuges (Solifugae). Most false scorpions were collected under bark. We only collected three harvestmen, mostly from leaf litter. Solifuges were disappointing. With only 31 species currently recorded from Angola, we hoped to augment the species list and species distribution data. Yet, irrespective of numerous traps put out at each site, and day and night searching, we

Ruan Booyesen sampling spiders in the grass at Cuanavale Lake, a source lake of the Okavango system. (Photo: TLB)

Ruan Booyesen collects spiders through beating in the forest. (Photo: TLB)

Uroplectes occidentalis Simon, 1876 (Buthidae), a forest species, often found on dead wood and up tree trunks. (Photo: RB)

The recently described *Ceratogyrus attonifer* Engelbrecht 2019 (Theraphosidae) (Photo: TLB).

collected only two specimens, a *Biton* Karsch, 1880 (Daesiidae) female and a possible *Solpugema* Roewer, 1933 (Solpugidae) juvenile. The latter was collected for us by a local Angolan who accidentally unearthed it while digging.

Solifuges are referred to as *Kalumba kamucala* in the local Umbundu language, meaning “something by the name of Kalumba that never stays on the same place”. Unfortunately, given that neither specimen was adult male, these cannot be identified to species. One possible reason for the few solifuge specimens collected could be that timing was not optimal. Greater understanding of solifuge biology in the Miombo systems would help to fine-tune collecting in these areas. Even the data associated with the two specimens collected during the expedition (i.e., habitat, microhabitat, life-stages) already contribute significantly towards that goal.

The most successful arachnid sampling were the spiders. The spider diversity in Angola is understudied with only around 270 species recorded for the region. Our sampling in the eastern parts of Angola resulted in representatives of 38 spider families collected during the expedition. Some notable finds include the recently-described horned baboon spider, *Ceratogyrus attonifer* Engelbrecht, 2019 (Theraphosidae), and another undescribed *Ceratogyrus* Pocock, 1897 species. Additionally, some other rare species were also collected such as the goblin spider genus *Orchestina* Simon, 1882 (Oonopidae), a very colourful jumping spider possibly in the genus *Chryssilla* Thorell, 1887 (Salticidae), the African wafer trapdoor spider genus *Ancylotrypa* Simon, 1889, some wolf spiders (Lycosidae) that mimic ants, and some long-spinnereted bark-spiders of the genus *Hersilia* Audouin, 1826 that decided the eroded soil banks are a great place to camouflage instead of their usual trees. This list only covers a very small portion of the groups collected, and a comprehensive list will be available at a later date.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S.¹, JOCQUÉ, R.², HADDAD C.R.³, FOORD, S.H.¹ † & LOTZ L.N.⁴ 2024. *The Zadariidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide. Part 1 (A-D) version 1: 1-91

The family is known from 97 species and 22 genera from South Africa.

Part 1: deals with genera A to D (73 species) and is available from the World Spider Catalog, Zenodo and Research Gate. I

Part 2 will be available early 2025.

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, R. Jocqué, C.R. Haddad, S.H. Foord & L.N. Lotz

SANSA Identification Photo Guide Version 1 (2024): 1-90